

TAGLE (Transformation Acquired from Good Learning Environment): THE DEVELOPED LOCALIZED SUPPLEMENTARY INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIALS FOR ARLING PANLIPUNAN 9 LEARNERS IN LOS BAÑOS NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL-POBLACION

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ABSTRACT

The main objective of the study was to developed Localized Supplementary Instructional Materials in Araling Panlipunan 9. This study aligned to the Design and Development Research Method design. Through a simple random sampling technique, the respondents of the study were 80 Grade 9 learners from Los Banos National High School Poblacion and 18 Araling Panlipunan secondary school teachers compose of Head Teacher, Master Teacher, Coordinator, and Araling Panlipunan Teachers from the District of Los Banos. Using four-point Likert Scale and the simple mean, t-test for independent samples findings revealed that the developed localized supplementary instructional materials in Araling Panlipunan 9 based on the assessment of the Araling Panlipunan teachers in terms of objectives, directions, topics and practical exercises were all highly valid. Meanwhile, the level of acceptability of the developed localized supplementary instructional materials in Araling Panlipunan 9 were all highly valid based on the assessment on the Araling Panlipunan teachers in terms of clarity, usefulness, presentation, and suitability. There was a significant difference in the academic performance level of the learners comparing the mean scores of the learners during the pretest and posttest. The developed localized supplementary instructional materials in Araling Panlipunan 9 evidently increased the acquisition of learning of Grade 9 learners based on the difference in their performance in the pretest and posttest.

Keywords: Localized Supplementary Instructional Materials in Araling Panlipunan 9, *effectiveness of instructional materials, impact of LSIM.,motivational, validation*

INTRODUCTION

Within the Philippine educational landscape, the subject of Araling Panlipunan 9 occupied a central role in fostering socio-cultural awareness and historical understanding among students. However, prevailing pedagogical practices often struggled to bridge the gap between standardized curriculum materials and the rich tapestry of Filipino cultural heritage (Bueno & Bueno, 2019). As a result, students found themselves disengaged from the learning process, unable to fully connect with the subject matter on a personal or cultural level.

The backdrop against which this study unfolds is the dynamic educational landscape of Los Baños National High School-Poblacion (LBNHS-Poblacion), situated in the vibrant community of Los Baños, Laguna, Philippines. LBNHS-Poblacion stands as a microcosm of the broader educational challenges and opportunities facing Filipino learners in the 21st century. Within this context, Araling Panlipunan 9 holds particular significance, serving as a conduit for imparting socio-cultural awareness, historical consciousness, and civic engagement among students.

Despite the vital role of Araling Panlipunan 9, the standardized nature of existing instructional materials did not fully resonate with the unique cultural backgrounds and experiences of students at LBNHS-Poblacion, hindering their engagement and comprehension of the subject matter (Ballesteros, 2020). Moreover, the geographic and socio-economic diversity within the student body of LBNHS-Poblacion presented additional challenges in ensuring equitable access to quality education (Department of Education, 2019).

In response to these challenges, this study seeks to embark on a transformative journey aimed at the development and validation of localized supplementary instructional materials for Araling Panlipunan 9 specifically tailored to the learners of LBNHS-Poblacion. By centering the study on the focal perspective of students in Los Baños, Laguna, the research endeavors to bridge the gap between standardized curriculum materials and the experiences of learners, thereby fostering a more inclusive and culturally responsive learning environment.

This study is motivated by the need to address the gap between standardized instructional materials and the diverse cultural backgrounds of students at LBNHS-Poblacion. The development and validation of localized supplementary instructional materials for Araling Panlipunan 9 aim to enhance students' engagement and comprehension of the subject matter, promote equity in education, and empower students as active participants in their learning journey. Through collaboration with educators, community stakeholders, and students themselves, this study aims to co-create instructional materials that not only align with the Araling Panlipunan 9 curriculum but also

reflect the cultural richness and diversity of the local context. By engaging in a participatory and iterative development process, the study seeks to empower students as co-creators of knowledge, enabling them to see themselves reflected in the educational materials and fostering a sense of ownership and pride in their learning journey.

The synthesis of the reviewed literature on the development and validation of localized supplementary instructional materials for Araling Panlipunan 9 revealed significant insights into their creation, validation, and impact on teaching and learning outcomes. Studies by Pardilla and Santos (2020), Lacanilao and Manalastas (2023), Bellido and Rico (2021), and Dianti et al. (2023) highlighted the importance of expert validation, practicality, and targeted interventions in developing effective instructional materials. Ferdiyanto and Kholili (2022), Dayta (2020), Lorbis (2019), and Olokooba (2021) further demonstrated the value of tailored materials in addressing student needs, while Tompong and Guanzon (2024) and Mayos et al. (2023) underscored their role in improving academic performance. Badidles and Quimbo (2021) also revealed the existing gap in appropriate instructional materials aligned with curriculum standards. Flores (2021) and Edinyang et al. (2020) explored the contextualization, fundamental role, awareness, content, and utilization of instructional materials/resources in achieving effective social studies education.

On the validation front, insights from Kleinheksel et al. (2020), Salzberger and Koller (2019), and Husain et al. (2021) emphasized the critical role of content validity in ensuring alignment with educational goals. Jalotjot (2023) and Tolentino et al. (2020) stressed the importance of thorough validation processes, while Patni et al. (2020) and Ka et al. (2023) highlighted the need for clarity and appropriateness in instructional materials. Rogayan and Dollete (2019), Gumonan and Bug-os (2021), and Espiritu and Ogerio (2020) all provided evidence of the effectiveness and contextualized validated materials in enhancing academic performance, further corroborating the importance of content validity. Tolentino (2023), Tukiran et al. (2020), Kobandaha et al. (2022), and Wadhono et al. (2023) elaborated that effective instructional materials enhanced students' self-efficacy, learning outcomes, and experiences.

Moreover, literature accentuated the significance of localized supplementary instructional materials in various educational contexts. Saro et al. (2023), Matewos et al. (2019), and Alqasham (2023) showcased their potential in improving learning outcomes and fostering learner autonomy. Harwood (2021) emphasized the need to understand instructional materials within their contextual framework, while Noor and Purnamasari (2019) advocated for incorporating local context learning materials to promote cultural comprehension. Cempron (2021) underscored the vital role of instructional materials in Social Studies education, particularly in online learning environments, while Omojemite et al. (2022) highlighted the influence of teachers' qualifications on effective material utilization.

Collectively, these insights bridged gaps in the study by providing a comprehensive understanding of the development, validation, and contextual relevance of localized supplementary instructional materials. They underscored the importance of rigorous

validation processes, alignment with educational objectives, and contextual considerations in enhancing teaching and learning outcomes. By incorporating these findings, the study leveraged the best practices and methodologies to develop and validate effective instructional materials tailored to the needs of Araling Panlipunan 9 learners.

This study addressed a synthesis gap by integrating and building upon existing research on the development, validation, and contextual application of localized supplementary instructional materials. The synthesis of multiple studies provided a comprehensive framework for understanding best practices and methodologies in creating instructional materials that meet the diverse needs of learners and align with educational goals.

The purpose of this study was to develop localized supplementary instructional materials for Araling Panlipunan 9 at Los Baños National High School-Poblacion, with a specific focus on addressing the economic contexts and learning needs of the students. The study aimed to contribute to the economic efficiency of education by ensuring that the developed materials were cost-effective and sustainable for implementation within the school setting. Variables considered in the study included economic factors such as the availability of financial resources for instructional material development, the cost-effectiveness of different materials and delivery methods, and the economic impact of improved learning outcomes on students' prospects.

The research design incorporated an economic analysis component to assess the financial implications of developing and implementing localized supplementary instructional materials. This analysis considered factors such as the initial investment required for material development, ongoing maintenance costs, and the potential return on investment in terms of improved student achievement and long-term economic benefits. By incorporating economic considerations into the study design, the research aimed to provide valuable insights into the cost-effectiveness of educational interventions and inform decision-making processes within the school and broader educational community.

The locale of the study, Los Baños National High School-Poblacion, situated in the vibrant community of Los Baños, Laguna, Philippines, offered a rich socio-economic context for the research. Los Baños was known for its diverse economic activities, including agriculture, tourism, and research institutions, providing a varied economic landscape for the study to explore. By focusing on a locale with diverse economic characteristics, the study aimed to ensure the relevance and applicability of the findings to a range of economic contexts within the Philippines and beyond.

Respondents in the study included students enrolled in Araling Panlipunan 9 at Los Baños National High School-Poblacion, as well as educators and experts in economics and education. Students served as the primary beneficiaries of the developed instructional materials, with their economic backgrounds and learning needs informing the design and implementation process. Educators provided valuable insights into the

economic realities of teaching and learning at the school, while experts in economics and education served as validators, ensuring the relevance and effectiveness of the materials from an economic perspective. Through collaboration with educators and experts, the study aimed to develop instructional materials that not only addressed economic contexts but also contributed to improved learning outcomes and economic opportunities for students.

Research Objectives

The study developed localized supplementary instructional materials tailored to the unique cultural contexts and learning needs of students at Los Baños National High School-Poblacion for the subject of Araling Panlipunan 9. It addressed gaps in existing instructional materials by creating culturally responsive and engaging supplementary materials specifically designed for learners at Los Baños National High School-Poblacion. By enhancing the effectiveness and relevance of Araling Panlipunan 9 instruction through the development and validation of localized supplementary instructional materials, the study empowered educators and students at Los Baños National High School-Poblacion to foster active learning, critical thinking, and socio-cultural awareness in the classroom.

Specifically, the following were the determined research objectives:

1. Design and develop localized supplementary instructional materials for Grade 9 Araling Panlipunan in Los Baños National High School-Poblacion.
2. Determine the level of validity and acceptability of the developed localized supplementary instructional materials for Grade 9 Araling Panlipunan in Los Baños National High School-Poblacion.
3. Determine the significant difference between the pretest and posttest results in the utilization of the developed localized supplementary instructional materials of Grade 9 learners in Los Baños National High School-Poblacion.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research design employed in this study was the Design and Development Research Method. The decision to adopt this approach was informed by its recognized efficacy in addressing practical challenges within educational contexts, particularly in the creation of instructional materials. McKenney and Reeves (2019) emphasized the pertinence of Design and Development Research in educational interventions, highlighting its capacity to systematically design, implement, and evaluate innovative solutions, thereby facilitating iterative refinement based on feedback and evidence.

Furthermore, this approach harmonized with fundamental principles of instructional design and educational technology. According to Gray et al. (2022), Design and Development Research emphasized the systematic development of instructional materials grounded in learning theories, pedagogical principles, and design best practices. By adhering to a rigorous development process, the study ensured that the instructional materials were firmly rooted in educational principles, thereby fostering desired learning outcomes effectively.

Overall, the Design and Development Research approach was well-suited for the current study as it furnished a structured framework for systematically developing and validating localized supplementary instructional materials for Araling Panlipunan 9. By adhering to this approach, the researchers ensured that the materials were finely tailored to the specific needs and context of learners at Los Baños National High School, thereby enhancing their relevance and effectiveness in supporting student learning.

Research Locale

The research was conducted at Los Baños National High School-Poblacion, specifically in the Poblacion area of Los Baños, Laguna, Philippines. The selection of Los Baños National High School-Poblacion as the research locale was guided by several criteria. Firstly, Los Baños National High School-Poblacion was one of the prominent secondary educational institutions in the locality, providing access to a diverse student population representative of the community. Secondly, the school administration expressed willingness to participate in educational research endeavors, facilitating access to resources and cooperation from key stakeholders.

However, it was essential to note that the research was limited to Los Baños National High School's Poblacion campus, despite the existence of another branch in the Batong Malake area. This restriction was due to logistical constraints and the focus on a specific demographic within the Los Baños community. By selecting the Poblacion campus, the study aimed to ensure homogeneity in the sample population and maintain consistency in data collection procedures. Additionally, focusing on one campus allowed for more manageable oversight and coordination throughout the research process.

Population and Sampling

The population of interest for this study consisted of Grade 9 learners at Los Baños National High School-Poblacion, specifically those enrolled in the Poblacion campus. The Poblacion campus comprised approximately 200 Grade 9 learners, distributed across five sections, with each section accommodating around 40 learners. In selecting participants for the study, a stratified random sampling technique was employed to ensure adequate representation from each section. Stratified random sampling involved dividing the population into homogeneous subgroups, or strata, based on specific characteristics relevant to the research. In this case, the five sections served as the strata, with each section representing a distinct subgroup within the Grade 9 population.

From each section, a proportionate number of students were randomly selected to participate in the study. This sampling approach enabled the inclusion of students from different sections, thereby capturing a diverse range of perspectives and experiences. By employing stratified sampling, the study aimed to ensure that the sample was representative of the entire Grade 9 population at Los Baños National High School-Poblacion campus while still maintaining the overall integrity of the research findings.

The Stratified Proportional Random Sampling technique was used to ensure students selected from each class or section reflected the total number of learners in the population and had the opportunity of being selected. This was done by dividing the total population in each section/class multiplied by the desired proportion of 40% of the population in order to come up with the sample size for the study ($n \times S/ N$). However, the computed sample size was 80 learners to address the rippling effect of 'non-response, incomplete or spoiled responses, attrition, and sampling mortality.

This approach was supported by literature emphasizing the importance of stratified proportional random sampling in ensuring representative samples in educational research (Qualtrics, 2023). Additionally, the use of proportional allocation aligned with established principles of sampling methodology, ensuring that each stratum was adequately represented in the sample. Overall, this sampling strategy enhanced the validity and generalizability of the study's findings, allowing for meaningful insights into the experiences and perspectives of Grade 9 learners at Los Baños National High School.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of the study were Grade 9 learners enrolled at Los Baños National High School's Poblacion campus. The selection criteria for participants included being currently enrolled in Grade 9 at the specified campus during the academic year corresponding to the study period (S.Y. 2023-2024). Additionally, participants were required to provide informed consent or approval, depending on their age, to voluntarily participate in the research activities.

The study aimed to include a representative sample of Grade 9 learners from each section of the Poblacion campus to ensure diversity and inclusivity in the research findings. This approach allowed for the inclusion of learners with varying backgrounds, academic abilities, and experiences, contributing to the richness and comprehensiveness of the data collected.

The involvement of Grade 9 learners as respondents was essential to the study as they were the primary beneficiaries and users of the localized supplementary instructional materials being developed and validated. Their perspectives, preferences, and feedback were crucial for informing the design, development, and validation processes, ultimately ensuring the relevance, effectiveness, and acceptability of the materials in supporting their learning needs.

Furthermore, the inclusion of Grade 9 learners as respondents aligned with the study's overarching goal of enhancing the quality of education and learning outcomes in Araling Panlipunan 9 at Los Baños National High School-Poblacion. By actively involving learners in the research process, the study aimed to empower them as stakeholders in their own education, fostering a sense of ownership and engagement in the learning process.

Table A

Respondents of the Study

Grade 9 Learners Per Section	Total Population	Sample Size	Percentage
1) Narra	40	16	20 %
2) Kamagong	40	16	20 %
3) Molave	40	16	20 %
4) Ipil-ipil	40	16	20 %
5) Acacia	40	16	20 %
Total	200	80	100%

Table A illustrated the distribution of respondents across different Grade 9 sections in the study. Each section, including Narra, Kamagong, Molave, Ipil-ipil, and Acacia, represented a distinct group of learners. The total population column indicated the number of students in each section, ranging from 40 to 40, with a total population of 200 across all sections. From these sections, a sample size of 16 learners was selected to participate in the study, resulting in a total sample size of 80.

The selection of 16 respondents from each section ensured adequate representation of the entire Grade 9 population while maintaining consistency across all sections. This approach helped minimize bias and ensured that findings were reflective of the broader student population.

Additionally, the percentage column provided insight into the proportion of the total population accounted for by the sample from each section. Each section contributed 20% to the overall sample size, indicating a balanced distribution of participants across the Grade 9 level. Overall, Table A offered a comprehensive overview of how the sample was distributed among different sections, demonstrating inclusivity and representation in the study's findings. This systematic sampling approach enhanced the validity and reliability of the study results, enabling researchers to draw meaningful conclusions about the Grade 9 population at Los Baños National High School-Poblacion.

Instrument

The research instrument utilized in this study was designed based on the developed localized supplementary instructional materials for Araling Panlipunan 9 to

gather data on various aspects related to the development and validation of localized supplementary instructional materials for Araling Panlipunan 9. The questionnaire comprised multiple sections, translated into the local vernacular, and each focused on specific dimensions relevant to the research objectives.

The first section of the questionnaire collected demographic information from the respondents, such as their grade level, age, gender, and academic performance. This demographic data helped provide context and allowed for the stratification of responses based on relevant variables.

The subsequent sections of the instrument were intended to evaluate the alignment and adoption of the various facets within the developed localized supplementary instructional materials for Araling Panlipunan 9. They encompassed aspects such as content alignment, clarity, comprehensiveness, adherence to curriculum standards, and effectiveness in enhancing learning outcomes. Participants were asked to assess these materials based on their clarity, thoroughness, alignment with curriculum standards, and their potential to improve learning outcomes.

To ensure the validity and reliability of the instrument, it underwent rigorous validation procedures. Expert reviewers, including subject matter experts and instructional design specialists, evaluated the questionnaire for content validity, ensuring that it adequately covered the relevant domains and measured the intended constructions. Additionally, a pilot test was conducted with a small sample of respondents to assess the clarity, comprehensibility, and relevance of the questionnaire items.

The finalized questionnaire incorporated feedback from the validation process and pilot testing, ensuring that it was clear, concise, and suitable for capturing the perspectives and insights of the target respondents. Data gathered through the questionnaire were subjected to statistical analysis to identify patterns, trends, and associations relevant to the research objectives.

Moreover, the research instrument utilized in this study integrated the Likert Scale, augmented by verbal interpretations, to facilitate the quantitative analysis of responses and achieve a comprehensive understanding of the development and validation of localized supplementary instructional materials for Araling Panlipunan 9 at Los Baños National High School-Poblacion. This methodological approach enabled a systematic evaluation of the effectiveness and suitability of the instructional materials in enhancing students' learning experiences and outcomes.

Validation of the Instrument

In this study, the validation of the research instrument was crucial to ensure its reliability and validity in gauging the intended constructs associated with the development and validation of localized supplementary instructional materials for Araling Panlipunan 9 at Los Baños National High School-Poblacion. The validation process comprised several

crucial steps aimed at assessing the instrument's efficacy in capturing pertinent variables and yielding dependable data for analysis.

Firstly, content validity was established by engaging fifteen (15) subject matter experts in Araling Panlipunan education and instructional design as interrater. These experts meticulously reviewed the research instrument to ascertain its comprehensive coverage of essential aspects concerning instructional material development and validation, ensuring alignment with curriculum standards and learning objectives.

Following this, construct validity was evaluated by administering the research instrument to a pilot sample of Grade 9 learners at Los Baños National High School-Poblacion. This pilot testing phase aimed to uncover any ambiguities or inconsistencies in the instrument's items and instructions, facilitating necessary revisions to bolster clarity and comprehensibility.

Moreover, criterion-related validity underwent scrutiny through the comparison of responses obtained from the research instrument with external criteria or benchmarks pertaining to student achievement, satisfaction, and engagement with the instructional materials. This comparative analysis served to validate the instrument's capability to accurately measure the intended variables and outcomes.

Lastly, reliability testing was conducted to gauge the internal consistency and stability of the research instrument over time. This entailed administering the instrument to a sample of Grade 9 learners on multiple occasions and employing statistical techniques such as Cronbach's alpha to ascertain the degree of reliability and consistency in their responses.

Overall, the validation process affirmed the research instrument's suitability and efficacy in measuring the constructions pertinent to the study's objectives. By ensuring the instrument's reliability and validity, researchers instilled confidence in the accuracy and integrity of the data collected, thereby augmenting the credibility and rigor of the study's findings.

Data Gathering Procedure

The data gathering procedure for this study was meticulously planned to ensure comprehensive data collection. Initially, permissions were obtained from relevant authorities, including school administrators and teachers, to conduct the study at Los Baños National High School-Poblacion. Once approval was secured, the researchers proceeded to schedule data collection sessions with Grade 9 learners.

To maintain a conducive environment for data collection, sessions were conducted in controlled classroom settings to minimize distractions and enhance participant focus and engagement. Before administering the survey questionnaire, clear instructions were provided to participants regarding the study's purpose, the voluntary nature of their participation, and the confidentiality of their responses.

The survey questionnaire, meticulously developed based on the research objectives and validated instruments, was then distributed to Grade 9 learners. Ample time was allotted for participants to read and respond to the questionnaire items. Student research assistants were on hand to address any queries or concerns raised by participants during the data collection process. Upon completion of the survey questionnaire, responses were collected and reviewed for completeness and consistency, with any missing or unclear responses clarified with participants where feasible.

Following the data collection phase, responses underwent coding, tallying, and careful scrutiny to ensure accuracy and reliability. Additionally, the collaboration extended to seeking assistance from the school statistician for data treatment and statistical analysis. This collaborative effort ensured that the data were handled and analyzed appropriately, culminating in valid and robust research findings.

RESULTS

Employing a systematic approach, the researcher organizes the data for a thorough examination, intending to shed light on the correlation between the developed instructional materials and their effectiveness in enhancing learning outcomes. Through rigorous scrutiny of the findings, significant patterns and trends emerge, enriching the understanding of how these materials could have benefited the learners of Los Baños National High School.

Research Objective 1. Determine the validity of contents of the developed localized supplementary instructional materials for Grade 9 Araling Panlipunan at Los Baños National High School in terms of:

1.1 Objectives

Table 1.1

Level of Content Validity of the Developed Localized Supplementary Instructional Materials for Grade 9 Araling Panlipunan in terms of Objectives

Indicators	$\bar{X}$	VI
1. Relevant to the topics in Grade 9	4.00	HV
2. Specific and clearly Stated	4.00	HV
3. Measurable, attainable. And result-oriented	4.00	HV
4. Well-planned, formulated, and organized	4.00	HV
5. Time bound	4.00	HV
General Assessment	4.00	HV

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Highly Valid (HV) 2.50-3.24 Valid (V) 1.75-2.49 Partially Valid (PV) 1.00-1.74 Not Valid (NV)

Objectives was **Highly Valid (4.00)** as to the level of content validity of the developed localized supplementary instructional materials for Grade 9 Araling Panlipunan. However, **all indicators** received a composite mean score of **4.00** verbally interpreted as **Highly Valid**.

Specifically, the materials are deemed highly relevant to the topics covered in Grade 9, with objectives that are specific, clearly stated, measurable, attainable, result-oriented, well-planned, formulated, organized, and appropriately time-bound.

Upon comprehensive analysis and interpretation of the data, it becomes evident that the developed localized supplementary instructional materials for Grade 9 Araling Panlipunan hold significant promise in enhancing the quality of education delivery. The consistently high ratings across all indicators underscore the meticulous efforts invested in their development, affirming their alignment with educational objectives and curriculum standards. The robust content validity observed in this evaluation not only attests to the effectiveness of the materials in meeting the instructional needs of Grade 9 students but also underscores their potential to serve as valuable resources for educators seeking to optimize teaching and learning experiences.

In conclusion, the findings underscore the importance of developing localized supplementary instructional materials that are not only aligned with curriculum objectives but also exhibit a high degree of content validity. Moving forward, educators and curriculum developers must continue leveraging such materials to enhance the effectiveness and inclusivity of educational practices, thereby fostering a conducive learning environment for all students. This was similar to what Kleinheksel et al. (2020) mentioned when they highlighted the significance of content validity, particularly concerning objectives, in ensuring the effective alignment of instructional materials with educational objectives and learning outcomes. The authors emphasized that validity pertained to the extent to which the content of a test or measurement instrument accurately represented the construct it intended to measure. In the realm of educational materials, content validity ensured that the objectives outlined in the materials accurately reflected the intended learning outcomes. The authors further noted that content validity was typically evaluated through expert judgment, wherein subject matter experts assessed instructional materials to ascertain if the content adequately addressed the specified objectives. This evaluation process involved carefully examining the alignment between the objectives and the content presented to ensure that the materials effectively covered the desired knowledge, skills, and competencies. Additionally, the authors underscored the importance of establishing clear and measurable learning objectives that aligned with instructional content.

1.2 Directions

Table 1.2

Level of Content Validity of the Developed Localized Supplementary Instructional Materials for Grade 9 Araling Panlipunan in terms of Directions

Indicators	$\bar{X}$	VI
1. Simple and clear	4.00	HV
2. Easy to follow	3.93	HV
3. Properly sequenced	4.00	HV
4. Can be done independently	4.00	HV
General Assessment	3.98	HV

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Highly Valid (HV) 2.50-3.24 Valid (V) 1.75-2.49 Partially Valid (PV) 1.00-1.74 Not Valid (NV)

Directions was **Highly Valid (3.98)** as to the level of content validity assessment of the developed localized supplementary instructional materials for Grade 9 Araling Panlipunan. Across all indicators, the materials received commendable scores within the **Highly Valid** range. Specifically, the indicators “Simple and clear”, “Properly sequenced”, and “Can be done independently” all gauged the highest mean score of **4.00**. Additionally, the indicator “Easy to follow” got the **lowest** mean score of **3.93**.

Upon comprehensive analysis and interpretation of the data, it is evident that the developed localized supplementary instructional materials for Grade 9 Araling Panlipunan, focusing on directions, hold significant potential in enhancing the quality of education delivery. The consistently high ratings across all indicators related to directions underscore the thorough efforts invested in their development, affirming their alignment with educational objectives and curriculum standards. The robust content validity observed in this evaluation not only attests to the effectiveness of the materials in meeting the instructional needs of Grade 9 students but also underscores their potential to serve as valuable resources for educators seeking to optimize teaching and learning experiences.

In conclusion, the findings emphasize the importance of developing localized supplementary instructional materials with clear and effective directions. These materials not only align with curriculum objectives but also exhibit a high degree of content validity. Moving forward, educators and curriculum developers must continue leveraging such materials to enhance the effectiveness and inclusivity of educational practices, thereby fostering a conducive learning environment for all students.

Salzberger and Koller (2019) emphasized the significance of considering the direction of the response scale in measurement, particularly in the context of assessing content validity. They highlighted that the directionality of the response scale played a crucial role in ensuring accurate measurement and interpretation of data. The authors underscored the importance of accounting for the unit of measurement when designing response scales, as it influenced respondents' perceptions and responses. They argued

that the direction in which the response options were presented could impact respondents' comprehension and decision-making processes. By aligning the response scale with the intended directionality of the construct being measured, researchers could enhance the validity and reliability of their assessments. Salzberger and Koller's insights shed light on the methodological considerations relevant to assessing content validity in instructional materials, emphasizing the need to carefully design response scales to optimize measurement accuracy and consistency.

1.3 Topics

Table 1.3

Level of Content Validity of the Developed Localized Supplementary Instructional Materials for Grade 9 Araling Panlipunan in terms of Topics

Indicators	X	VI
1. Sequenced according to curriculum	4.00	HV
2. Logically presented	4.00	HV
3. Address the learners' needs	3.93	HV
4. With background and concepts	4.00	HV
General Assessment	3.98	HV

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Highly Valid (HV) 2.50-3.24 Valid (V) 1.75-2.49 Partially Valid (PV) 1.00-1.74 Not Valid (NV)

Topics was **Highly Valid (3.98)** as of the level of content validity assessment of the developed localized supplementary instructional materials for Grade 9 Araling Panlipunan. Across all indicators, the materials received commendable scores within the **Highly Valid** range. Specifically, the materials were perceived as being sequenced according to the curriculum, logically presented, and provided adequate background and concepts were all achieving the **highest** mean score of **4.00**. Additionally, they effectively addressed the learners' needs, got the **lowest** mean score of **3.93**.

Upon comprehensive analysis and interpretation of the data, it becomes evident that the developed localized supplementary instructional materials for Grade 9 Araling Panlipunan, focusing on topics, hold significant assurance in enhancing the quality of education delivery. The consistently high ratings across all indicators related to topics underscore the painstaking efforts invested in their development, affirming their alignment with educational objectives and curriculum standards. The robust content validity observed in this evaluation not only attests to the effectiveness of the materials in meeting the instructional needs of Grade 9 students but also underscores their potential to serve as valuable resources for educators seeking to optimize teaching and learning experiences.

In conclusion, the findings accentuate the importance of developing localized supplementary instructional materials that effectively address topics aligned with curriculum objectives and exhibit a high degree of content validity. Moving forward, it remains imperative for educators and curriculum developers to continue leveraging such

materials to enhance the effectiveness and inclusivity of educational practices, thereby fostering a conducive learning environment for all students.

In support of the above findings, Husain et al. (2021) investigated the development of an Integration Self Learning (InSeL) Module for Matriculation Students, focusing on topics relevant to content validity. Their study explored the alignment between the instructional materials developed and the intended learning objectives, highlighting the importance of content validity in educational resource development. The authors emphasized the need to ensure that the content of the InSeL Module accurately reflected the desired learning outcomes and addressed the specific needs of matriculation students. By assessing content validity, they aimed to verify that the module effectively covered the intended topics and facilitated student learning. Husain et al.'s research underscored the significance of content validity in instructional material development, providing insights applicable to the present study's focus on the development and validation of localized supplementary instructional materials for Araling Panlipunan 9.

1.4 Practical Exercises

Table 1.4

Level of Content Validity of the Developed Localized Supplementary Instructional Materials for Grade 9 Araling Panlipunan in terms of Practical Exercises

Indicators	X̄	VI
1. In consonance with the objectives	4.00	HV
2. Appropriate to learners' abilities	4.00	HV
3. Adequate to enhance learners' comprehension and reading skills	4.00	HV
4. Sufficient to determine the mastery level of learners	3.93	HV
5. Stimulate higher order thinking skills	4.00	HV
General Assessment	3.99	HV

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Highly Valid (HV) 2.50-3.24 Valid (V) 1.75-2.49 Partially Valid (PV) 1.00-1.74 Not Valid (NV)

Practical Exercises was **Highly Valid (3.99)** as to the level of content validity assessment of the developed localized supplementary instructional materials for Grade 9 Araling Panlipunan. Across all indicators, the materials received commendable scores within the **highly valid** range. Specifically, the practical exercises were perceived as being in consonance with the objectives, appropriate to learners' abilities, adequate to enhance learners' comprehension and reading skills, and noted for their capacity to stimulate higher-order thinking skills, all evaluated at the **highest** mean score of **4.00**. Additionally, the practical exercises was noted for their sufficiency to determine the mastery level of learners, which achieved the **lowest** mean score of **3.93**.

Upon comprehensive analysis and interpretation of the data, it becomes evident that the developed localized supplementary instructional materials for Grade 9 Araling Panlipunan, focusing on practical exercises, hold significant potential in enhancing the quality of education delivery. The consistently high ratings across all indicators related to

practical exercises highlight the thorough efforts invested in their development, affirming their alignment with educational objectives and curriculum standards. The robust content validity observed in this evaluation not only attests to the effectiveness of the materials in meeting the instructional needs of Grade 9 students but also underscores their potential to serve as valuable resources for educators seeking to optimize teaching and learning experiences.

In conclusion, the findings accentuate the importance of developing localized supplementary instructional materials with practical exercises that are not only aligned with curriculum objectives but also exhibit a high degree of content validity. Moving forward, it remains imperative for educators and curriculum developers to continue leveraging such materials to enhance the effectiveness and inclusivity of educational practices, thereby fostering a conducive learning environment for all students.

This is relative to what Patni et al. (2020) examined in the development of content and online discussion strategies in blended learning to enhance student mathematical learning outcomes, focusing on practical learning exercises relevant to content validity. Their study emphasized the importance of ensuring that the instructional materials and online discussion strategies effectively align with the intended learning objectives and facilitate student engagement. By addressing content validity, the authors aimed to verify that the practical learning exercises incorporated into the blended learning approach adequately cover the key mathematical concepts and promote meaningful learning experiences. Patni et al.'s research underscores the significance of content validity in instructional design, providing insights applicable to the present study's focus on developing and validating localized supplementary instructional materials for Araling Panlipunan 9.

1.5 Clarity

Table 1.5
Level of Content Validity of the Developed Localized Supplementary Instructional Materials for Grade 9 Araling Panlipunan in terms of Clarity

Indicators	$\bar{X}$	VI
1. Information is clear and simple	4.00	HV
2. Language used is clear and easy to understand	4.00	HV
3. The concepts for each activity are re-arranged logically and ensure that there is no duplication	4.00	HV
4. Information suits learners' interest.	4.00	HV
General Assessment	4.00	HV

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Highly Valid (HV) 2.50-3.24 Valid (V) 1.75-2.49 Partially Valid (PV) 1.00-1.74 Not Valid (NV)

Clarity was Highly Valid (4.00) the level of content validity assessment of the developed localized supplementary instructional materials for Grade 9 Araling Panlipunan. Across all indicators related to clarity, the materials received commendable scores within

the **Highly Valid**. Specifically, the materials were perceived as presenting information that is clear and simple, the language used was reported to be clear and easy to understand, materials were noted for their logical arrangement of concepts for each activity, ensuring no duplication and facilitating a coherent learning experience, and the materials were found to suit learners' interests, **all** received the **highest** mean score of **4.00**.

Upon comprehensive analysis and interpretation of the data, it becomes evident that the developed localized supplementary instructional materials for Grade 9 Araling Panlipunan, focusing on clarity, hold significant potential in enhancing the quality of education delivery. The consistently high ratings across all indicators related to clarity underscore the diligent efforts invested in their development, affirming their alignment with educational objectives and curriculum standards. The robust content validity observed in this evaluation not only attests to the effectiveness of the materials in meeting the instructional needs of Grade 9 students but also underscores their potential to serve as valuable resources for educators seeking to optimize teaching and learning experiences.

In conclusion, the findings underscore the importance of developing localized supplementary instructional materials that are clear, comprehensible, and engaging for students. These materials not only align with curriculum objectives but also exhibit a high degree of content validity in terms of clarity.

This is parallel to what Ka et al. (2023) investigated on the development of task-based instructional e-modules for the data processing unit of information technology courses, with a focus on clarity in instructional materials. Their study emphasized the importance of content validity in ensuring that instructional materials are clear and comprehensible to learners. By incorporating clear and concise instructions, explanations, and examples into the e-modules, the authors aimed to enhance the clarity of the instructional materials and facilitate student understanding. Ka et al.'s research highlights the relevance of content validity to the present study's focus on developing and validating localized supplementary instructional materials for Araling Panlipunan 9, particularly in ensuring clarity and comprehensibility for Grade 9 learners.

Research Objective 2. Establish the level of acceptability of the developed localized supplementary instructional materials for Grade 9 Araling Panlipunan, ensuring that they effectively address the curriculum requirements and meet the diverse learning needs of students at Los Baños National High School in terms of?

2.1 Usefulness

Table 2.1

Level of Acceptability of the Developed Localized Supplementary Instructional Materials for Grade 9 Araling Panlipunan in terms of Usefulness

Indicators	$\bar{X}$	VI
1. The materials prepares the learners to think logically and critically	4.00	VA
2. The concepts in the material are simple and comprehensible	4.00	VA
3. The material helps the students master the topics at their own pace	4.00	VA
4. The material provides opportunity for the development	4.00	VA
5. The learning contents provide adequate information on the topics presented	4.00	VA
6. The material motivates learners to become actively involved in the learning activities	4.00	VA
7. The material stimulates the learners to intellectual activities which help them master the least learned competencies	4.00	VA
8. The activities seek to relate new concepts from previous learning	4.00	VA
General Assessment	4.00	VA

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Very Acceptable (VA) 2.50-3.24 Acceptable (A) 1.75-2.49 Partially Acceptable (PA) 1.00-1.74 Not Acceptable (NA)

Usefulness was **Very Acceptable (4.00)** as to the level of acceptability of the developed localized supplementary instructional materials for Grade 9 Araling Panlipunan. Across **all indicators** related to usefulness, the materials received commendable scores of **4.00** verbally interpreted as **Very Acceptable**.

Specifically, the materials prepare learners to think logically and critically, present concepts that are simple and comprehensible, help students master topics at their own pace, provide developmental opportunities, offer adequate information on the presented topics, motivate learners to become actively involved in learning activities, stimulate intellectual activities, and relate new concepts to previous learning. All these achievements receive the highest mean score of 4.00, interpreted as very acceptable (VA).

Upon comprehensive analysis and interpretation of the data, it becomes evident that the developed localized supplementary instructional materials for Grade 9 Araling Panlipunan, focusing on usefulness, hold significant potential in enhancing the quality of education delivery. The consistently high ratings across all indicators related to usefulness underscore the thorough efforts invested in their development, affirming their alignment with educational objectives and curriculum standards. The robust acceptability observed in this evaluation not only attests to the effectiveness of the materials in meeting the instructional needs of Grade 9 students but also underscores their potential to serve as valuable resources for educators seeking to optimize teaching and learning experiences.

In conclusion, the findings highlight the importance of developing localized supplementary instructional materials that are useful, engaging, and effective for students. These materials not only align with curriculum objectives but also exhibit a high degree of acceptability in terms of usefulness.

This was relative to what Rogayan and Dollete (2019) embarked on in the development of a workbook in physical science for Senior High School (SHS) students, focusing on the least learned concepts identified among students in a government-owned university in Central Luzon, the Philippines. The authors found that the developed workbook garnered high acceptability from expert validators, with an average rating of 3.90. Specifically, the workbook was deemed acceptable in terms of adequacy (M = 3.85), coherence (M = 3.90), appropriateness (M = 3.90), and usefulness (M = 3.95). The validated material was recommended for use as a supplemental instructional tool in physical science courses in SHS. Moreover, the workbook, grounded in the analysis, design, development, implementation, and evaluation (ADDIE) model, could serve as a prototype for developing workbooks for other courses in the K-12 SHS curriculum. It was suggested that further review and evaluation of the workbook be conducted to enhance its contextualization, localization, and indigenization within the Philippine educational context.

2.2 Presentation

Table 2.2

Level of Acceptability of the Developed Localized Supplementary Instructional Materials for Grade 9 Araling Panlipunan in terms of Presentation

Indicators	X	VI
1. The topics are presented in logical and sequential order	4.00	VA
2. The direction is concise readable, and easy to follow	4.00	VA
3. The topics fit the learners' needs	4.00	VA
4. The presentation of each lesson is attractive and interesting	4.00	VA
General Assessment	4.00	VA

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Very Acceptable (VA) 2.50-3.24 Acceptable (A) 1.75-2.49 Partially Acceptable (PA) 1.00-1.74 Not Acceptable (NA)

Presentation was Very Acceptable (4.00) as to the level of acceptability of the developed localized supplementary instructional materials for Grade 9 Araling Panlipunan. Across **all indicators** related to presentation, the materials received commendable scores within the **Very Acceptable**.

Upon comprehensive analysis and interpretation of the data, it becomes clear that the developed localized supplementary instructional materials for Grade 9 Araling Panlipunan, with a focus on presentation, hold substantial promise in enhancing the quality of education delivery. The consistently high ratings across all indicators related to presentation underscore the meticulous efforts invested in their development. This

suggests that the materials are thoughtfully designed and organized to effectively convey the intended content to students. Additionally, the alignment of the materials with educational objectives and curriculum standards further solidifies their efficacy. The robust acceptability observed in this evaluation not only confirms the effectiveness of the materials in meeting the instructional needs of Grade 9 students but also highlights their potential to serve as valuable resources for educators. By providing engaging and well-structured instructional materials, educators can optimize teaching and learning experiences in the classroom. These materials have the capacity to foster student engagement, promote comprehension, and ultimately contribute to improved academic outcomes. Therefore, the positive evaluation results underscore the significance of investing in the development and utilization of high-quality instructional materials to enhance the overall educational experience for students and educators alike.

In conclusion, the findings highlight the importance of developing localized supplementary instructional materials that are presented effectively and engagingly for students. These materials not only align with curriculum objectives but also exhibit a high degree of acceptability in terms of presentation. Moving forward, it remains imperative for educators and curriculum developers to continue leveraging such materials to enhance the effectiveness and inclusivity of educational practices, thereby fostering a conducive learning environment for all students.

This was related to what Espiritu and Ogerio (2020) mentioned when they examined the process of creating contextualized learning materials by investigating the strategies and resources utilized in developing teacher-made materials for Social Studies 9 (Economics) in a Zambales school district, Philippines. The study aimed to evaluate the acceptability of these materials among teacher specialists and secondary students in the area. The authors identified five main approaches used by teachers to contextualize learning materials: place, student context, pedagogy, disciplinary content, and cultural or learner diversity. Place-based contextualization involved incorporating information from the local environment, community issues, daily events, and existing structures into the lessons. Student context considerations utilized the interests and experiences of learners to tailor lessons accordingly. Teachers, the school, and the community emerged as primary resources in the material preparation process. While the crafted materials generally met criteria for readability, content, computerization, diversity of learners, and presentation, the authors highlighted the need for further enhancement in contextualization. As a recommendation, they emphasized the importance of providing increased training and support for teachers to develop and utilize contextualized materials effectively in addressing students' needs.

2.3 Suitability

Table 2.3

Level of Acceptability of the Developed Localized Supplementary Instructional Materials for Grade 9 Araling Panlipunan in terms of Suitability

Indicators	X	VI
1. Activities consider the varying attitudes and capabilities	4.00	VA

2. Activities are appropriate to the subject matter	4.00	VA
3. Activities are relevant, interesting, and self-motivating to the learners	4.00	VA
4. Enrichment activities cater the different learning needs of learners	4.00	VA
5. Language of the program is within the vocabulary range of learners	4.00	VA
General Assessment	4.00	VA

Legend: 3.25-4.00 Very Acceptable (VA) 2.50-3.24 Acceptable (A) 1.75-2.49 Partially Acceptable (PA) 1.00-1.74 Not Acceptable (NA)

Suitability was **Very Acceptable (4.00)** as the level of acceptability of the developed localized supplementary instructional materials for Grade 9 Araling Panlipunan. Across all indicators related to suitability, the materials received commendable scores of 4.00 verbally interpreted as **Very Acceptable**.

Upon comprehensive analysis and interpretation of the data, it becomes evident that the developed localized supplementary instructional materials for Grade 9 Araling Panlipunan, focusing on suitability, hold significant promise in enhancing the quality of education delivery. The consistently high ratings across all indicators related to suitability underscore the systematic efforts invested in their development, affirming their alignment with educational objectives and curriculum standards. The robust acceptability observed in this evaluation not only attests to the effectiveness of the materials in meeting the instructional needs of Grade 9 students but also underscores their potential to serve as valuable resources for educators seeking to optimize teaching and learning experiences.

In conclusion, the findings highlight the importance of developing localized supplementary instructional materials that are suitable, engaging, and effective for students. These materials not only align with curriculum objectives but also exhibit a high degree of acceptability in terms of suitability. Moving forward, it remains imperative for educators and curriculum developers to continue leveraging such materials to enhance the effectiveness and inclusivity of educational practices, thereby fostering a conducive learning environment for all students."

This was parallel to what Tolentino et al. (2023) undertook in the development of a booklet geared towards undergraduate teacher education research, which underwent validation by experts and intended users from a state-run university in Central Luzon, Philippines. The primary objective was to enhance and facilitate a more efficient and effective teaching and learning approach for undergraduate research subjects through the utilization of this supplementary learning material. The developmental process adhered to the analysis-design-development-implementation-evaluation (ADDIE) model. The study found that, overall, instructional materials for undergraduate research were perceived to be somewhat available and moderately adequate by the respondents. Expert validators affirmed that the booklet was highly acceptable in terms of adequacy, coherence, appropriateness, and usefulness. Pre-service teachers evaluated the material, its modules, and lessons with considerable acceptability.

Research Objective 3. Determine the significant difference between the pretest and posttest results in the utilization of the developed localized supplementary instructional materials of Grade 9 learners in Los Banos National High School Poblacion in terms of:

3.1 Pretest Evaluation

Table 3.1
Level of Performance of Grade 9 Araling Panlipunan in the Pretest Evaluation

Section	Mastered		CAM		MTM		Average		Low		Very Low		Total
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
ACACIA	0	0	0	0	0	0	19	47.5	21	52.5	0	0	40
IPIL-IPIL	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	10	35	87.5	1	2.5	40
KAMAGONG	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	12.8	32	82.1	2	5	39
MOLAVE	0	0	0	0	0	0	7	17.5	32	80	1	2.5	40
NARRA	0	0	0	0	0	0	8	20	30	75	2	5	40
General Assessment	0	0	0	0	0	0	43	21.5	150	75	6	3	199

Legend: Mastered (M) 96 - 100% Closely Approximating Mastery (CAM) 86 - 95% Moving Towards Mastery (MTM) 66 - 85% Average (AVR) 35 - 65% Low (L) 15 - 34 % Very Low (VL) 5 - 14%

Overall, across all sections, no learners achieved mastery, closely approximated mastery, or were moving towards mastery. The majority of learners demonstrated average performance, with a smaller percentage showing low or very low performance.

This data suggests that there is room for improvement in the efficacy of the developed localized supplementary instructional materials for Grade 9 Araling Panlipunan. Further analysis and adjustments may be necessary to better support student learning and achievement.

It can be concluded that the data indicate a significant portion of the students do not meet the expectations set by the Department of Education. This underscores the necessity for supplementary instructional materials aimed at enhancing their performance. It is apparent that the current materials may not fully align with the learning needs and comprehension levels of the students, necessitating the development of additional resources tailored to address areas where students are struggling. These supplementary materials may be designed to provide targeted support and reinforcement to help students achieve mastery of the subject matter.

This was similar to what Tukiran et al. (2020) mentioned when they investigated the effectiveness of instructional materials in improving students' self-efficacy and understanding of acid-base concepts using the 9E learning cycle model. The study's focus on pre-test evaluation aligned with the exploration of the efficacy of developed instructional materials. The pre-test evaluation served as an initial assessment to gauge

students' self-efficacy levels and comprehension of acid-base topics before the instructional intervention. By comparing pre-test results with post-test outcomes, the researchers aimed to evaluate the impact of the instructional materials on students' learning progress and self-efficacy development. The authors revealed significant improvements in students' self-efficacy levels following the implementation of the instructional materials and the 9E learning cycle model. Additionally, there was a noticeable enhancement in students' comprehension of acid-base concepts, indicating the efficacy of the developed instructional materials in facilitating learning and bolstering self-efficacy among students. These findings underscored the importance of well-designed instructional materials in promoting student learning and confidence in challenging subject areas like acid-base chemistry.

3.2 Posttest Evaluation

Table 3.2

Level of Performance of Grade 9 Araling Panlipunan in the Posttest Evaluation

Section	Mastered		CAM		MTM		Average		Low		Very Low		Total
	F	%	F	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
ACACIA	7	17.9	18	46.2	14	35.9	0	0.0	0	0	0	0	39
IPIL-IPIL	8	21.1	4	10.5	19	50.0	7	18.4	0	0	0	0	38
KAMAGONG	4	10.8	6	16.2	24	64.9	3	8.1	0	0	0	0	37
MOLAVE	4	10.3	3	7.7	28	71.8	2	5.1	0	0	0	0	37
NARRA	4	10.5	16	42.1	18	47.4	0	0.0	0	0	0	0	38
General Assessment	27	14.3	47	24.9	103	54.5	12	6.3	0	0	0	0	189

Legend: Mastered (M) 96 - 100% Closely Approximating Mastery (CAM) 86 - 95% Moving Towards Mastery (MTM) 66 - 85% Average (AVR) 35 - 65% Low (L) 15 - 34 % Very Low (VL) 5 - 14%

General Assessment of the **Posttest Evaluation** for the level of Performance of Grade 9 Araling Panlipunan, **14.3%** from different sections **Achieved Mastery, 24.9% closely approximated mastery**, A smaller percentage, **6.3 %**, fell into the **average category**, while no students were in the low or very low category. Across others, varying levels of mastery and comprehension are evident among the students.

The post-test evaluation indicates notable improvements in students' comprehension levels compared to the pretest evaluation. While some variability exists across sections, the majority of students are either moving toward mastery or closely approximating it. These results suggest that the developed localized supplementary instructional materials have effectively facilitated learning and comprehension among Grade 9 Araling Panlipunan students.

This was relative to what Wadhono et al. (2023) mentioned when they conducted a study focusing on the development of telegram learning media, acknowledging the

existing deficiency in students' listening and critical thinking skills. Their research aimed to evaluate the quality of this media in terms of its practicality, validity, and effectiveness. Through the development of telegram learning media, it was anticipated that students' learning experiences would be enhanced. The data collection methods employed in their investigation included questionnaires, pre-test and post-test assessments, validation sheets, and observational data. Their findings indicated that the development process followed the stages of analysis, design, development, implementation, and evaluation, highlighting the systematic approach taken in refining the learning media. The authors also observed that the post-test evaluation revealed notable improvements in students' comprehension levels after engaging with the telegram learning media. This indicated that the developed instructional materials effectively contributed to enhancing students' listening and critical thinking skills. The study findings suggested that telegram learning media held promise as an effective tool for facilitating learning and addressing deficiencies in students' skills.

3.3 Pretest and Posttest Evaluation

Table 3.3

Test of Significant Difference between the Pretest and Posttest Evaluation

Indicators	Test	Paired Differences				Remarks	Decision
		Mean	SD	t	P value		
Araling Panlipunan 9	Pre & Post	- 27.12	5.79	- 64.091	.000	Significant	Reject H_0

There was a significant difference between the pretest and posttest evaluation of data. The paired differences between the pretest and posttest scores show a mean difference of **-27.12**, with a standard deviation of **5.79**. The calculated t-value is **-64.091**, and the corresponding p-value is **.000**, indicating a significant difference between the pretest and post-test scores. Based on the significant p-value, the null hypothesis was rejected. This suggested that there was a significant improvement in the efficacy of the developed localized supplementary instructional materials from the pretest to the posttest evaluation for Grade 9 Araling Panlipunan.

The significant improvement in the efficacy of the developed localized supplementary instructional materials for Grade 9 Araling Panlipunan, as indicated by the pretest and post-test evaluation, holds several implications for educational practice. Firstly, the observed increase in student performance underscores the effectiveness of these materials in facilitating learning outcomes. This suggests that the materials are well-designed and aligned with the curriculum objectives, enabling students to better comprehend and master the subject matter. Moreover, the positive results suggest that these materials have the potential for sustained use in Grade 9 Araling Panlipunan classes, offering educators a valuable resource to enhance teaching and learning experiences.

Furthermore, the notable improvement in student learning outcomes highlights the importance of investing in high-quality educational resources. By allocating resources towards the development and implementation of effective instructional materials, educational institutions may foster improved academic achievement among students. Additionally, the findings imply an opportunity for further development and refinement of the materials. Educators and curriculum developers can use insights gained from the evaluation to address remaining gaps or challenges and optimize the efficacy of the materials even further.

Conclusions

In conclusion, the findings from the pretest and post-test evaluation underscore the significance and effectiveness of the developed localized supplementary instructional materials for Grade 9 Araling Panlipunan. These materials demonstrate their ability to enhance student learning outcomes and align with curriculum objectives. Continued investment in the development and refinement of such materials is essential to further improve the quality of education delivery and contribute to the academic success of students.

In support of the above findings, Kobandaha et al. (2022) conducted a literature review focusing on the development of digital media and Ludo Ekponen to enhance learning outcomes among Grade IX junior high school students. Their study aimed to examine the effectiveness of these instructional materials through pre-test and post-test evaluations. The authors developed digital media and Ludo Ekponen as supplementary learning resources and assessed their impact on students' learning outcomes. Prior studies emphasized the importance of utilizing innovative instructional materials to improve learning outcomes in educational settings. Digital media and gamified learning approaches, such as Ludo Ekponen, showed promise in engaging students and enhancing their academic performance. By integrating these instructional materials into the learning process, educators could create dynamic and interactive learning experiences that catered to the diverse needs of students. The authors highlighted the need for empirical research to evaluate the efficacy of digital media and gamified learning approaches in improving learning outcomes among junior high school students. Studies suggested that these instructional materials could foster active learning, critical thinking,

Recommendations

Use this LSIM

**THE DEVELOPED LOCALIZED SUPPLEMENTARY INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIALS
FOR ARALING PANLIPUNAN 9 IN LOS BANOS NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL-
POBLACION**

ARALING PANLIPUNAN 9 EKONOMIKS IKA-APAT NA MARKAHAN

Modyul Para sa Mag-aaral

Nilikha ni
Gng. Julia T. Field

PAGSULONG AT PAG-UNLAD NG BAYAN NG LOS BANOS

Mga Layunin:

Sa araling ito, inaasahang ...

- matutukoy ang mga palatandaan ng pag-unlad ng bayan ng Los Banos.
- makapagbibigay ng sariling pakahulugan sa pag-unlad.
- matutukoy ang mga gampanin ng mamamayan sa pag-unlad ng bayan ng Los Banos
- mapapahalagahan ang kasaysayan ng pag-unlad at pagsulong ng bayan ng Los Banos.
- mababatid ang mga naging hakbang ng pamahalaan ng Los Banos tungo sa kaunlaran.

Mahahalagang Terminolohiya

- pag-unlad
- pagsulong

Pagpapahalaga:

- paggalang sa kultura
- pagtanaw sa nakaraan

Week 1-2

main street Circa cctophillpanaglimavolanta.wordpress.com

Circa Road

Gawain sa Pagkakatuto Bilang 1

Sagutan ang mga tanong, Isulat ang sagot sa kuwaderno

1. Ano ang iyong opinyon sa 2 larawan nasa itaas?

2. Kailan masasabing may pag-unlad ang isang bayan?

3. Masasabi mo bang nagkaroon ng pagsulong base sa mga larawan? Bakit?

Ang pag-unlad at pagsulong ay magkapareho lamang sa kataga kung ang pagbabatayan natin ay tungo sa pag-angat ng antas o lebel ng pagbabago. Ngunit malaki ang pagkakaiba ng dalawang salitang ito.

Ang Kaunlaran ay tumutukoy sa paggamit ng mga makabagong teknolohiya, pangkalahatang pagbuti ng antas ng pamumuhay. Ang pagsulong sa ekonomiya ay masasalamain sa positibong pagbabago para sa lahat.

Paano nga ba nagkaroon ang pag-unlad at pagsulong ang bayan ng Los Banos noong hindi pa isinisilang ang mga tinatawag natin ngayon "Millenials"?

Kasaysayan ng Los Banos bago ang Kaunlaran

Ang bayan na ito ay matatagpuan malapit sa paanan ng Bundok Makiling. Ito ay tinaguriang baryo *Mainit* ng bayan ng Bay na napapaligiran ito ng mga bukas ng tubig na nangagaling sa Natugbos o kung tawagin ay *Mud Spring* (isang maliit na lawa ng kumukulong putik) at umaagos patungong baybayin ng Laguna de Bay. Hindi pa man dumarating ang mga Kastila sa ating bansa ay hayag na sa mga Katutubong Pilipino ang mga katangiang taglay ng maligamgam na bukal ng tubig na lubhang nakatutulong sa pagpapagaling ng

mga ilang uri ng sakit.

Noong taong 1589 isang paring Franciscano na nagngangalang Pedro Bautista ang nag sa publikong ng paliguan sa lugar na ito hanggang sa tawaging "Los Banos". Itinayo ang gusaling yari sa kawayan at kugon na siyang nagsilbing tirahan ng mga pasyenteng dumarayo sa bayan na ito upang malunasan ang kanilang karamdaman.

mga gusalling yari sa kawayan at kugon

Source: Discovering the old Philippines

Ang Baryong ito ay kilala sa tawag na Mainit dahil na rin sa taglay nitong maligamgam na bukal ng tubig. Taong 1615, ika 17 ng Setyembre, nang magkaroon ng kasarinlan at napahiwalay sa bayan ng Bay sa ilalim ng rebolusyong itinatag ng isang Kastila na si Don Luis Villa. Mula sa pangalang Mainit ay pinalitan ito ng Los Banos na pinamunuan ng kaunahanang kapitan o gobernadorcillo ng bayan (na ngayon ay alkalde o mayor kung tawagin) na si Don Juan Castaneda.

Taong 1671, nagtayo ang mga paring Franciscano ng ospital kasabay din ang simbahan sa karangalan ng mahal na Patron ng Immaculada Conception na noong panahong iyon ay tinagurian Nuestra Senyora de Agua, santang ipinagdiriwang tuwing Disyembre 8 ang kapistahan.

Pag-unlad ng bayan

Sa hindi inaasahang pagkakataon, nasunog ang gusali ng Ospital kasama rin ang simbahan noong 1727, at minabuting muling magpatayo ng simbahan sa karangalan pa rin ng Mahal na Birhen Nuestra Senora de Agua Santa. na sa simula ay yari sa Nipa at kawayan ang simbahan. Ang natutunghayan nating simbahan ngayon ay ang itinayo noong 1790 na yari sa bato sa pangunguna ni Padre Domingo Mateo.

unang batong simbahan ng Los Baños Source: Discovering the old Philippines

Ang sakristiya at tore ay itinatag naman noong 1852, sa pangunguna ni Padre Manuel Amat. Ngunit tulad ng karamihan ng mga simbahan sa Laguna, laging nasisira ito ng mga lindol ngunit pinagsisikapan naman na muling maitayo.

gusali ng Agua Santa, source: salt & light.com

Mula sa Kawayan at kugon na gusali ito ay pinalitan ng yari sa bato dahil na rin sa sunog na naganap sa Ospital at simbahan. Taong 1879 nang ipinatayo ang isang gusali at pinangalanan ng **Agua Santa** na nagsilbing pagamutan. Naging sentro ng turismo ang Los Baños dahil narin sa iba't ibang tao at pari ang doo'y nahihimlay panandalian hanggang sa sila ay gumaling sa kanilang mga karamdaman. Noong 1909, ang Kolehiyo ng Agrikultura ng Unibersidad ng Pilipinas ay itinatag sa Los Baños. Ang paunang organisasyon ng institusyong ito ay sinimulan noong huling bahagi ng parehong taon. Ito ay naging isa sa mga mahalagang katangian ng sistema ng Unibersidad.

pinangalanan ng *Agua Santa* na nagsilbing pagamutan. Naging sentro ng turismo ang Los Banos dahil narin sa iba't ibang tao at pari ang doo'y nahihimlay panandalian hanggang sa sila ay gumaling sa kanilang mga karamdaman. Noong 1909, ang Kolehiyo ng Agrikultura ng Unibersidad ng Pilipinas ay itinatag sa Los Baños. Ang paunang organisasyon ng institusyong ito ay sinimulan noong huling bahagi ng parehong taon. Ito ay naging isa sa mga mahalagang katangian ng sistema ng Unibersidad.

[lupaing pag-aari ng UPCA](#) source: [orerbil.blogspot.com](#)

[gusali ng UPCA](#) source: [orerbil.blogspot.com](#)

Ang Kolehiyo ng Veterinary Science ay binuksan sa Maynila noong mga kalagitnaan ng taong 1910 at, noong 1920, ang lokasyon nito ay inilipat sa Los Banos, Laguna, malapit sa Kolehiyo ng Agrikultura. Gayundin sa lokasyong ito at sa mga lupaing pag-aari ng Bureau of Forestry at katabi ng Colleges of Agriculture and Veterinary Science, ang School of Forestry ay itinatag noong 1916.

Gawain sa Pagkakatuto Bilang 2

Ang mga kaalaman na natutuhan ang magiging gabay sa pagpapaliwanag ng mga sagot. Gumamit ng sagutang papel sa pagsasagot sa mga tanong.

1. Magbigay ng isang palatandaan ng pag-unlad ng bayan ng Los Banos noong dekada 1600 at ipaliwanag kung paano nagkaroon ng pagunlad sa bayan na ito?

Gawain sa Pagkakatuto Bilang 3

Piliin sa loob ng kahon ang wastong sagot at isulat sa sagutang papel.

Padre Pedro Bautista	Mainit	Agua Santa	Kapistahan
Don Juan Castaneda	Kolehiyo ng Agrikultura		Padre Manuel Amat
Kasarinlan ng bayan	Padre Domingo Mateo		Gobernadorcillo

- _____ 1. Okasyon ang ipinagdiriwang tuwing Disyembre 8?
- _____ 2. Unang katawagan sa bayan na ngayon ay tinawag na Los Banos.
- _____ 3. Kaunaunahang gobernadorcillo ng Los Banos
- _____ 4. Siya ang paring nagsa publiko ng paliguan
- _____ 5. Pangyayaring naganap sa bayan ng mainit noong Setyembre 17, 1615.
- _____ 6. Pangalan ng gusali yari sa bato na ipinatayo noong taong 1879 .
- _____ 7. Siya ang paring nanguna sa pagtatag ng sakristiya at tore noong taong 1852.
- _____ 8. Mahalagang sistema ng Unibersidad ng Pilipinas.
- _____ 9. Tawag na namumuno sa isang bayan noong panahon ng kastila.
- _____ 10. Siya ang paring nanguna sa pagpapatayo ng unang simbahang bato sa Los Banos noong taong 1790.

Gawain sa Pagkakatuto Bilang 4

Pagbubuod sa pang unawa : Sagutin ang mga katanungan ayon sa inyong pang-unawa isulat ang sagot sa sagutang papel.

1. Magbigay ng isang hakbangin na ginawa ng mga namamahala ng bayan para sa kaunlaran ng bayan ng Los Banos. Ipaliwanang sagot.

2. Para sa iyong pang unawa ibigay ang kahulugan ng Pag-unlad at pagsulong.

3. Bilang mamamayan tama mahalaga ba na malaman ang kasaysayan ng pag-unlad ng iyong bayan?

5

Gawain sa Pagkakatuto Bilang 4:

Pagbubuod sa pang unawa: Sagutin ang mga katanungan ayon sa inyong pang-unawa isulat ang sagot sa sagutang papel.

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3. Bilang mamamayan tama mahalaga ba na malaman ang kasaysayan ng pag-unlad ng iyong bayan?

KALAGAYAN NG AGRIKULTURA SA BAYAN LOS BANOS

Week 3-4

Mga Layunin:

- Sa araling ito, inaasahang ...
- masusuri ang bahaging ginagampanan ng agrikultura sa ekonomiya ng bayan ng Los Banos
 - masusuri ang epekto at dahilan ng sektor ng agrikultura sa pamumuhay ng mamamayan.
 - mabibigyan ng kahalagahan ang sektor ng agrikultura.
- Makabubuo ng desisyon sa pagsusulong ng agrikultura sa pamayanan.

Mahahalagang Terminolohiya

- agrikultura
- International Rice Research Institute
-

Pagpapahalaga: paggalang sa

- kultura pagtanaw sa
- nakaraan

Gawain sa Pagkakatuto Bilang 1

uplb.edu.ph/college

UPLB Gate

Sagutan ang mga katanungan at isulat ang sagot sa sagutang papel:

1. Kung inyong susuriin saan lugar ang mga nasa larawan

2. Ano ang mga sinisimbulo ng mga nasa larawan?

3. Ano ang kahalagahan ng mga nasa larawan sa agrikultura dito sa ating bayan?

6

Kasaysayan ng Agrikultura sa Los Baños, Laguna

source: Wikimapia Bundok Maria Makiling

Kilala ang Los Baños sa kanyang bundok/bulkan, ang Bundok Maria

Makiling. Maging si Rizal ay namasyal dito at nagsulat rin ng kwento tungkol sa diwatang si Maria Makiling na tagapangalaga ng kalikasan ng nasabing bundok. Itinalaga ito ng Amerikanong botanista at agrikulturistang si Edwin Copeland noong Marso 6, 1909 bilang Kolehiyo ng Agrikultura, isa sa unang dalawang yunit ng Unibersidad ng Pilipinas o *University of the Philippines College of Agriculture* (UPCA). Nagsimula ang klase noong Hunyo 1909 na may limang propesor at 12 na mag-aaral lamang. Ang Paaralang Palagubatan (Forestry School) ay itinatag sa sumunod na taon.

Raid sa Los Baños Noong 1909. Ang UPCA ay nasira nang nagsimula ang Pananakop ng mga Hapon sa Pilipinas, at ang paaralan ginawang punong tanggapan ng mga Hapon. Unidos ng First Battalion, 511th Parachute Infantry Regiment ng

Sa mahigit ng tatlong taon, ang unibersidad ay naging tahanan ng mahigit 2,000 sibilyan, karamihan ay Amerikano, na dinakip ng mga Hapon.

Ang UPCA ay naging isang bilanggo sa giyera ng Hapon, Nagsagawa ng isang plano ang punong tanggapan ng isang lihim na samahan ng mga gerilya upang mapalaya ang mga bihag ng hapon. Noong 23 Pebrero 1945, ang mga puwersa ng Estados

Eleventh Airborne Division ay namuno sa isang pinagsamang amphibious at airborne raid laban sa kampo ng bilangguan, nasagip ang higit sa 2000 na Allied nationals. Pinatay nila ang 250-taong Japanese garison. Upang mapilit ang mga bilanggo na iwanan ang kanilang mga pag-aari at mapabilis ang paglisan bago magpadala ang mga Hapones ng mga bala, sinunog ng mga puwersa ng US at mga gerilyang Pilipino ang kampo. Ang Baker Hall lamang, ang gymnasium sa unibersidad hanggang 2010, ay nanatiling buo.

lunang gusali ng baker hall; courtesy U.S. Signal picture

Ang Agrikultura sa Los Banos, Laguna

Ayon sa dyornal na isinulat ni Gloria o Green Revolution, lumikha ito ng Esguerra Melencio, (2019) Pag aari ng iba't ibang uri kanin o bigas na may mga Domikanong pari ang Laguna. Isa mataas na ani na ginagamit sa iba't sa mga paborito nilang pasyalan ang Los ibang bansa sa Asya.

Banos dahil sa mainit na bukal nito na kung saan doon nagbababad ang mga ito. Kaya't ang mga pari ay nag-utos na magtanim dito ng maraming puno.

Maraming tao ang naging hanap-buhay [larawan ng mga banyaga sa IRRI](#) ccto: IRRI ay pagkaka ingin at pangingsda dahil na Tunay nga na ang bayan ng Los Banos rin sa ang bayan na ito ay malapit ay mayaman sa kalikasan hindi lamang lamang sa lawa ng Laguna. Sa paanan sa pagsasaka nabubuhay ang mga tao ng bundok Makiling ang siyang naging sa bayan na ito, dahil na rin sa

[karatig taniman ng mga naninirahan dito.](#)

[paanan ng bundok Makiling sa Los Banos.](#); ccto travel blog

Ang bundok Makiling ay isang bulkan [hindi](#) aktibo, sabi sa alamat ito ay hugis babaeng natutulog, siya ang dalagang si Makiling. Ang Unibersidad ng Pilipinas ang siyang nangangalaga dito. Upang mas higit [na](#) mapalawig at maragdagan ang kaalaman sa agrikultura. Itinatag ang *International Rice Research Institue (IRRI)* noong 1960 sa tulong ng Ford Foundation at Rocket Foundation ng Estados Unidos. Nag ambag ang IRRI noong

1960-1970 ng Rebolusyon Berde nito ang Laguna de Bay, isa sa hanap buhay ng mga tao rito ay ang pangingsda, sagana sa mga likas na yaman noong dekada 1960. Sa Artikulo [ni](#) Krizza Bauto ng Los Banos Times, naging bahagi ng mga residente na naninirahan malapit sa lawa ang pangingsda, ito ang kanilang hanapbuhay na minana na rin sa kanilang mga magulang. Ayon nga sa kanyang artikulo, may isang mangingsda ang kanyang sinamahan sa pangingsda at doon na rin ininterbyu. Sa pagitan ng 1970 at 1980 ang lawa ay masagana pa sa huling isda, kung saan ang mga baybayin ay hindi pa sementado, iba ang ganda ng lawa, malinaw ang tubig at maraming matatabang isda nahuhuli.

[Laguna ng Laguna sa Los Banos.](#) 4 square

May isang lugar o Purok sa Brgy. Bambang ito ay kung tawagin ay Quarry. karatig nito ang Dampalit Falls na dinarayo ng maraming tao, isang kaaya ayang lugar na kung saan sagana sa tubig talon. Lubhang makasaysayan ang bayan ng los Banos dahil na sa ka akit akit na ganda ng bayan na ito naging mabilis ang pag-ulad nito at maraming pagbabago, sa pagbabagong iyon unti unti rin nasira ang kalikasan, ang dating sariwa at matatabang

General view, Los Banos Quarry. Los Banos, isda ang nahuhuli sa lawa ngayon ay unti

General view, Los Banos Quarry. Los Banos, Laguna. 1934, (Bureau of Highways) unti rin nawala, ang bundok na idinaos ang pag ka quarry ay unti unti na rin dumami ang mga naninirahan, na sa tuwing mayLaguna. 1934, (Bureau of Highways) bagyo o nagkakaroon ng malakas na pag ulan ay maaring magdulot ng landslide na ikapapahamak ng mga naninirahan doon. Lubhang naapektuhan ang Dampalit Falls sa pagdami ng mga naninirahan sa Quarry, dahil doon sila kumukuha ng tubig na siyang ginagamit nila sa kanilang pang-araw araw na pamumuhay. Humina ang dating malakas na rumaragasang tubig sa talon dahil na rin sa kanya kanyang kabit ng tubo upang dumaloy sa kanilang mga tahanan. **Kahalagahan ng Agrikultura**

1. **Nagpapasok ng Dolyar sa bansa** - dahil na rin sa mga kalidad na produkto gawa sa Pilipinas banyaga man o mamamayang Pilipino, kumikita ang bansa ng dolyar na siyang nagpapataas ng ating ekonomiya na dumadaloy sa mga lalawigan at mga bayan ng Laguna
2. **Bumibili ng mga produkto ng industriya** - Ang mga produkto ng Agrikultura na tinatangkilik ng mga Industriya (Hal. buko at prutas) ay ginagamit upang iproseso sa industriya.

Dayagram 1

3. Nagbibigay ng hanapbuhay - Pangunahing hanapbuhay saagrikultura ay ang pagsasaka, paghahayupan at pangingisda na kung saan ang mga mamamayan ng Los Banos ang sentro sa pag gawa **Mga Suliranin ng Agrikultura**

1. **Paglago ng Populasyon** - sa pag daan ng mga taon ang Populasyon ng mga naninirahan sa bayan ng Los Banos ay lumobo ang mga lupang dating ginagamit sa sakahan ay naging tirahan ng mga nag migrasyon sa bayan na ito, dahil na rin sa kakulangan ng impormasyon ng pangangalaga ng ating kalikasan kaya't marami sa bahagi ng Laguna de Bay na nasasakupan ng bayan ay marami ng basura dahilan sa polusyon. sa Talaan 1 makikita ang paglago ng populasyon ng bayan ng Los Banos simula Taong 2015 hanggang 2020.

Talananayan 1

Table 11. Annual Population Growth Rate, Year 2015 and 2020

Barangay	Population percentage [2020]	Population [2020]	Population (2015)	Change (2015-2020)	Annual Population Growth Rate [2015-2020]
Anos	7.64%	8,815	8,039	9.65%	1.96%
Bagong Silang	0.61%	707	629	12.40%	2.49%
Bambang	5.62%	7,638	7,228	5.67%	1.17%
Batong Malake	10.90%	12,578	15,314	-17.87%	-4.06%
Baybayin	1.27%	1,466	1,692	-10.17%	-2.23%
Blog	10.07%	11,613	10,460	11.02%	2.23%
Lalakay	3.67%	4,234	5,032	-15.86%	-3.57%
Maahas	7.62%	8,785	7,536	16.57%	3.28%
Malinta	5.66%	6,531	7,368	-11.36%	-2.51%
Mayondon	15.45%	17,817	17,071	4.37%	0.90%
Putho Tuntungin	8.06%	9,300	9,068	2.56%	0.53%
San Antonio	13.85%	15,978	13,537	18.03%	3.55%
Tadlak	3.50%	4,043	3,319	21.81%	4.24%
Timugan	5.07%	5,848	5,775	1.26%	0.26%

Source: Philippine Statistics Authority (Census of Population, 2015)

2. **Pagpapasemento ng mga baybayin** - ayon na rin sa ulat sa LB Times isang mangingisda ang nagsabi na dati rati masagana ang paghuli ng mga isda sa lawa ngunit dahil na rin sa mabilis na pagsulong ng bayan at pagbabago ng anyo ng baybayin ng lawa maliit na pursyento na lamang ang nagiging huli ng mga isda.

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3. Paglaganap ng mga Imported Goods - Isang malaking hamon sa bayan ng Los Banos ang pag-usbong ng mga imported goods dahil dito mas marami ang tumangkilik ng mga produktong banyaga.

4. Climate Change - Ito ay nagdudulot ng malawakang pagbabago sa mga patern ng panahon. Ang mga tag-init ay nagiging mainit na mainit, habang ang mga tag-ulan naman ay nagiging mapanglaw at maulan nang labis. Ang ganitong mga pagbabago ay naglilikha ng malalaking hamon para sa mga magsasaka ng Los Banos partikular na sa kanilang mga pananim na nagsisilbing kanilang pangunahing kabuhayan isa na rito ang taniman ng aster sa Brgy. Bayog.

Larawan ng taniman ng Aster sa Brgy. Bayog

Lubhang apektado rin ang mga isda, tulad ng tilapia at iba pang isdang tabang sa Climate change na nagaganap sa ating panahon. Kaakibat nito ay ang pagiging sensitibo nito sa pagbabagong panahon, na siyang nakakaapekto rin sa kabuhayan ng mga residente. Nakararanas ngayon ng krisis ang produksyon ng mga isda dahil hindi na umano kasing dami ng dati ang mga huli sa lawa nitong mga nakaraang taon bunsod ng abnormal na pagtaas at pagbaba ng temperatura. Ang dating 50% na nabubuhay na isda sa loob ng fish cages, ay bumaba sa 20% na lamang, na siyang nagdulot ng malaking kabawasan sa kanilang kinikita.

5. Pandemya - isang malaking dagok sa mga magsasaka at mangingisda ang malawakang Lock down marami sa kanila ang hindi naisagawa ang pagsasaka at pangangisda dulot ng pandemya. Marso 8, 2020 idineklarang nasa state of a public health emergency ang Pilipinas dahil sa pagdami ng kumpirmadong kaso ng Coronavirus (COVID-19) sa bansa. Mahigit isang taon din kinakaharap ng buong mundo ang pandemyang nagdulot ng banta, hindi lamang sa kalusugan ng mga mamamayan, kundi pati na rin sa kanilang kabuhayan.

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Gawain sa Pagkakatuto Bilang 2

Gamit ang Fishbone Pumili ng isa sa mga suliranin sa Agrikultura at isulat ang inyong ideya na makatutulong sa paglutas ng problema. Kumuha ng isang malinis na papel at isulat ang inyong sagot sa dayagram ng Fishbone.

Dayagram 2

Gawain sa Pagkakatuto Bilang 3.

Sagutin ang mga tanong sa kwadero

1. Anong A ang tumutukoy sa paghahalaman at pagpaparami ng alagang hayop?

2. Anong M ang ngalan ng bundok dito sa Los Banos?

3. Anong P ang hanap buhay sa lawa ng Laguna?

4. Anong G at R ang naimbag ng IRRI para sa pagkakaroon ng mataas ng ani ng palay

5. Anong B ang pangunahing sangkap ng produktong dinarayo sa bayan ng Los Banos?

Gawain sa Pagkakatuto Bilang 4

A. Sagutin ang mga katanungan

1. Paano natapos ang pag ho hostage sa mga Pilipino at banyagang Amerikano sa Baker Hall?

2. Ano ang ugnayan ng Agrikultura sa ibang pamilihan dito sa bayan ng Los Banos

3. Paano nakatutulong ang Agrikultura sa pagpasok ng Dolyar sa ating bansa?

4. Ano ang naiambag ng pagpapakatag Ng University of the Philippines College of Agriculture UPCA SA bayan?

5. Ano ang naging sanhi ng paglago ng Populasyon sa bayan ng Los Banos

B. Ibigay ang inyong opinyon tungkol sa isinagawang pagsasaliksik ng mga banyaga sa mga palay sa ating bansa? Makakatulong ba ito sa pagpapaunlad?

Gawain sa Pagkakatuto Bilang 5

Ilapat at isabuhay

A. Paano ka makatutulong upang mapaunlad ang sektor ng Agrikultura?

B. Pumili ng isa at isagawa ang mga gawain upang maipakita kung gaano mo naunawaan ang paksang tinalakay.

c. Sumulat ng tula ukol sa paraan ng iyong gagawin upang matulungan ang sektor ng agrikultura
Q magpakita ng isang role playig upang matulungan na umunlad ang sektor ng Agrikultura.

12

SEKTOR NG INDUSTRIYA SA BAYAN LOS BANOS

Sa araling ito, inaasahang ...

- mabibigyang-halaga ang mga ang mga gampanin ng sektor ng industriya at mga patakarang pang ekonomiya nakatutulong dito.
- mabibigyang-halaga ang mga patakarang pangekonomiya nakatutulong sa sektor ng industriya.
- masusuri ang

Mga Layunin: pagkakaugnay ng sektor

agrikultural at industriya tungo sa pag-unlad ng kabuhayan.

- **Mahalalagang Terminolohiya**
- produksyon industriya

Pagpapahalaga:

- paggalang sa kultura pagtanaw sa
- nakaraan

Gawain sa Pagkakatuto Bilang 1

Sagutan ang mga katanungan at

isulat ang sagot sa sagutang papel

1. Magbigay ng mga industriyang na matatagpuan dito sa Los Banos.
2. Paano nakatutulong ang sektor ng industriya sa pamayanan ng Los Banos?
3. Ano ano ang naidudulot ng industriya sa mamamayan ng Los Banos?

Ang nasa larawan ay ang Original Buko Pie na matatagpuan sa baranggay ng Anos, dinarayo ito ng mga tao dahil sa sarap ng buko pie na ito. Isa ito sa ipinagmamalaki ng bayan ng Los Banos. Hindi lang ang Original Buko Pie ang makikita sa barangay Anos, nariyan din ang Lety's Buko Pie, Mltz Bake shop (na kung saan ang kanilang *specialty ay cassava cake,*) naging sentro ng turismo ang barangay Anos sa mga dumadayo sa mga karatig bayan ng Los Banos, na kung saan sila ay dumadaan upang bumili ng pasalubong. sinasabi na ang Los Banos ay nakilala rin dahil sa mga masarap na kakanin at ito ay nakakatulong sa ekonomiya ng bayan dahil kahit sa ibang bansa ito ay nakararating na rin.

Kahalagahan ng Industriya sa pamayanan ng Los Banos

May pinakamalaking papel ang industriya na ginagampanan sa isang bayan lalo na sa ekonomiya. Sa bayan ng Los Banos karamihan sa mga industriya rito ay resosrt, na kung saan panahon pa ng mga Kastila dinarayo na ang bayan na ito dahil sa maligamgam na tubig at nakagagaling sa mga sakit. Ang mga bakeshop na may kanya kanyang espcialty na binabalik balikan ng mga turista banyaga man o lokal ang nagpapalawig ng kalakalan ng bayan. Malaking kontribusyon sa kaunlaran ng isang bayan ag industriya.

1. **Kumikita ng Dolyar** - Ang kalidad at lasa ng mga produkto na mula sa bakeshop ang kinagigiliwan ng mga mamimili hanggang sa umabot pa sa panlabas na sektor na kung saan ay maunlad pa rin. Malaki ang naitutulong nito sa pag pasok ng iba't ibang currency tulad ng Dolyar.
2. **Nagkakaloob ng Hanapbuhay** - dahil na rin sa pagdami ng industriya sa bayan marami sa mamamayan ng Los Banos ang nabigyan ng hanap buhay
3. **Nagpoproseso ng mga Hilaw na materyales** - malaking porsyento ng mga Materyales na galing sa sa sektok ng agrikultura ay ginagamit sa pagbuo ng produkto na poproseso sa Industriya. Isang halimbawa ang buko na siyang Pangunahing sangkap ng bukopie.

Pamamahagi ng Negosyo ayon sa Industriya

- Shopping: 18.7%
- Mga restawran: 14.5%
- Pagkain: 9.9%
- Hotels at Lakbayin: 9.6%
- Edukasyon: 8.2%
- Medikal: 6.8%
- Propesyonal na mga serbisyo: 6.2%
- Iba pa: 26.2%

Source: yellowpages

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INDUSTRIYA NG PAGHAHALAMAN

Nagsimula ang garden show bilang isang show-and-tell activity sa International Rice Research Institute (IRRI) noong dekada '60. Nagpasimula ang mga maybahay ng mga professor ng Unibersidad ng Pilipinas. Nang lumaon ay naging isa na itong simpleng samahan angkin ang layuning maipagmalaki ang kani-kanilang mga halaman. Noong 1972 nabuo ang Los Baños Orchid Society, o LBOS, dahil na rin sa pagpupursige ng mga datihang miyembro nito at sa patuloy na paglago ng ornamental horticulture. Hanggang sa ngayon patuloy pa rin ang organisasyon sa pagpapayabong ng mga ornamental na halaman.

Ang brgy. Bayog ay kilala sa taniman ng Aster na siyang pangunahing hanapbuhay ng karamihan naninirahan doon. Ilang dekada na rin ang dumaan at namana na rin ng mga anak hanggang sa apo ang pagtatanim ng aster.

INDUSTRIYA NG PAGGAGATAS

Taong 1923 ng mabuo ang kursong Animal Husbandry sa ilalim ng UPCA sa pamumuno ni Prof. Sam V. Durham. Dekada 60's ng lumawig ang kursong ito at naitatag ang DTRI sa taong 60's. Dekada 70's na ibinaba ang martial law at dito natigil ang operasyon. Taong 1975 inilunsad ang *new milk collection program* nakalaan sa likod-bahay, semi-komersyal, at komersyal na dairy farm. Ang mga maliliit na magsasaka ng pagawaan ng gatas pa rin ang pangunahing produkto nito. Bilang karagdagan sa pagawaan ng gatas, sinasaklaw nito ang mga pagsulong ng mga produktong gawa sa gatas kabilang ang nutrisyon, kalusugan, kalinisan sa kapaligiran, pagpapalano ng pamilya, produksyon ng pagkain, mga klase sa pananahi, at iba pang proyekto ng komunidad. Mula 1975-1979, isang American Peace Corps at ilang Japanese Overseas Cooperation volunteer ang idinetalye sa DTRI upang ibahagi ang kanilang kadalubhasaan.

Sa patuloy na pag-unlad ng bayan ng Los Banos maraming establisimento ang dito ay naitayo, naging sentro ng turismo ang dinarayong Buko pie ng Los Banos, iba't ibang uri ng kakanin na rin ang dito sa bayan na ito ang naitayo, cassava at yema cake. Nagkaroon rin mga Restaurant, tulad ng Dalampasigan Restaurant na nakabase sa Paciano Rizal Park, ang Ellen's Fried Chicken sa Grove, Batong Malake, Dumami na rin ang mga Resort na kung saan unang nakilala ang Agua Santa noong panahon pa ng Kastila, dito ay namalagi rin ang bayaning si Apolinario. Sunod sunod na pag-usbong ng mga establisimento. Ang mga kurso sa Unibersidad ng Pilipinas ng Los Banos ay nakahimpil sa baranggay Batong Malake ang siyang naging sentro ng pagpapatayo ng mga negosyo dahil na rin sa mga mag-aaral na galing pa sa iba't ibang lugar ng Pilipinas

Gawain sa Pagkakatuto Bilang 2

A. Tukuyin ang hinihingi ng sumusunod. Isulat ang wastong sagot sa sagutang papel.

- _____ 1. Anong Asosasyon ang nabuo sa industriya ng paghahalaman?
- _____ 2. Paano nakatutulong ang industriya sa Los Banos sa pamahalaan ng Los Banos?
- _____ 3. Ang DTRI ay pagawaan ng anong produkto na nabibili sa Los Banos?
- _____ 4. Anong halaman ang pangunahing pinagkakakitaan ng mga naninirahan sa barangay ng Bayog?
- _____ 5. Anong ginagawa ng industriya sa mga hilaw na materyales? Mga

Suliranin Kinaharap ng Industriya sa Los Banos

1. **Bakterya sa mga halaman** - taong 2016 nang tamaan ng Bacteria crown rot (BCR) ang mga halaman sa bayan ng Los Banos. *Red mites* ang itinuturing na pinagmulan ng Bacteria Crown Rot na siyang nagdulot ng paghina ng ani tulad ng papaya, buko, at iba pang mga gulay at prutas. Ayon sa pagsasaliksik ng DOSTPCARRD ang BCR ay maaring tuluyang makasira ng industriya ng mga bunga at halaman. Kapag ang puno ay nagkaroon nito, ang sanga, at ibang pang bahagi ay sumusuloy hanggang sa mabulok, bumabaho rin ang pagligid ng pinagtaniman nito.

2. **Pagsulpot ng mga imported Goods-** sa pag dating ng mga imported goods ay humina ang ilang industriya sa bayan ng Los Banos. Marami sa mga produkto na galing ibang bansa ay nakahiligan ng mga mamimili dahil na rin sa pagiging trending sa social media ng mga produktong galing sa ibang bansa. Hindi lamang sa mga tindahan na naririto sa bayan maging sa mga online shops ay makakabili rin ng mga produktong galing sa ibang larawan ng Korean Goods Store

sa Batong Malake bansa.

3. **Pandaigdigang Pandemya COVID-19** - Taong 2020, nang idineklara ang total Lock down sa buong mundo. Isa sa mga sektor ng Ekonomiya ang industriya na nawalan ng sigla marami sa mga industriya ang nagsara at tuluyang ng nalugi. Marami sa industriya ng Los Banos ay nanamlay at hindi na nakabangon o hindi na nakapagsimula pang muli dahil na rin sa pagkalugi ng biglaan Lock down.

Mga Hakbang na Isinagawa Upang Masolusyunan Ang Mga Suliranin Ng Industriya:

1. Taong 2016 nagkaroon ng pagsasaliksik ang DOST-PCARRD upang matugunan ang suliranin na dulot ng BCR o Bacteria Crown Rot sa mga halaman. Kaugnay nito ang mananaliksik mula sa Unibersidad ng Pilipinas Los Banos at Davao National Crop Research ay nagsagawa ng pag aaral ukol sa BCR upang mapiglan ito na siyang sisira sa industriya ng paghahalaman na pinagkukunan mga hilaw na materyales para sa bagong produkto.

2. Pagpapaigting ng kalidad sa mga produkto ay mas lalong pinahusay ng mga bahay kalakal at industriya.
3. Paglikha ng ibang produkto na siyang pupukaw sa panlasa ng mga mamimili.
4. Pagpapalakas ng promosyon o pagsasa-ayos ng mga signage na siyang magpapakilala sa mga produkto ay binigyang pansin.
5. Pagbubukas ng mga bagong establisimento.
6. Pagpapatupad ng bagong patakaran ng pamahalaan.

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4. Pagpapalakas ng promosyon o pagsasa-ayos ng mga *signage* na siyang magpapakilala sa mga produkto ay binigyang pansin.
5. Pagbubukas ng mga bagong establisimento.
6. Pagpapatupad ng bagong patakaran ng pamahalaan.

Gawain sa Pagkakatuto Bilang 3 : Kaalaman sa Tiyak na Bagay. Ibigay ang wastong sagot

- _____1. Bakteryang sumira sa mga halaman.
- _____2. Taon lumaganap ang COVID-19
- _____3. Ahensyang nagsagawa ng pananaliksik upang mapigilan ang kumakalat na Bakteryang sa halaman.
- _____4. Itinuturing na pinagmulan ng bakteryang halaman.
- _____5. Sila ang nagsagawa ng pag-aaral upang mapigilan ang bakteryang.

Gawain sa Pagkakatuto Bilang 4: Paano mo tutulungan ang sektor ng industriya sa bayan ng Los Banos na lumago?

Pumili ng isa sa mga gawain. Gamit ang rubric sa ibaba sa pagmamarka

Gawain 1	Gawain 2	Gawain 3
Gumawa ng isang awitin ukol sa industriya at ano ang magagawa mo upang tulungan ito	Magpakita ng video clip na nagpapakita ng paraan kung paano ka makatutulong sa industriya at ekonomiya	Magsasagawa ng panel discussion at talkayin mo kung paanomatutulungan ang sektor ng industriya

Rubric sa gawain

Kraytirya	Pinakamahusay (5)	Mahusay (3)	Kailangan pa ng Pag-unlad (1)
Pandalubhasang presentasyon	nagpakita ng kahusayan	limitado ang paksa	malayo sa paksa
Pamaraan ng paggamit ng salita	naging malikhain	may kalinawan ang kaisipan ngunit hindi naipaliwanag ng maayos	walng kaugnayan ang mga ginamit na kaisipan
Kaalaman sa paksa	nagpakita ng kahandaan at lawak ng kaalaman	gumamit ng limitadong puntos	Mababaw lamang ang inihayag na opinyon

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SEKTOR NG PAGLILINGKOD SA BAYAN LOS BANOS

Week 6-7

Mga Layunin:

Sa araling ito, inaasahang ...

- masusuri ang bahaging ginagampanan ng sektor ng paglilingkod.
- mapahahalagahan ang mga patakarang pang-ekonomiya na nakatutulong sa sektor ng paglilingkod.
- makapagbabahagi ng kaalaman tungo sa pag-unald ng industriya sa bayan ng Los Banos.

Mahalagang Terminolohiya

- white collar job
- blue collar job
- mangagawa

Pagpapahalaga:

- paggalang sa kultura
- pagtanaw sa nakaraan

Ang manggagawa ay mahalaga sa pag unlad ng ekonomiya ng isang bayan. Sila ay may malaking bahaging gampanan sa industriya. Sila rin ang naglilingkod sa salik ng produksiyon. Sila ay buhay at sandigan ng pag-unlad ng industriya ayon kay Karl Marx, ang manggagawa ang tunay na prodyuser ng bansa. Isa mahalagang salik ng produksiyon ay ang paggawa (*labor*). Nangangahulugan ito na kailangan ang manggagawa sa transpormasyon o pagbabagong anyo ng mga hilaw na materyales sa pagbuo ng tapos na produkto. Lubos na napakikinabangan ang ibang saik ng produksiyon sa tulongng paggawa. Ito ang paggamit ng lakas, kakayahan at talino ng tao upang makatulong sa produksiyon. Naisasakatuparan ang mga gawaing pag-ekonomiya sapagkat sa lubos na paggamit ng mga manggagawa ng kanilang lakas at kakayahan upang makalihka ng mga produkto at serbisyo.

Gawain sa Pagkakatuto Bilang 1

source. LB PESO

Sagutan ang mga katanungan at isulat ang sagot sa sagutang papel

1. Ano ang mensahe na nais iparating ng nasa larawan?
2. Paano magiging epektibo ang anunsiyo ito sa mamamayan ng Los Banos?

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Pagtanaw sa nakaraan

Ang manggagawa ay mahalaga sa pag-unlad ng ekonomiya ng isang bayan. Sila ay may malaking bahaging gampanan sa industriya. Sila rin ang naglilinig sa salik ng produksiyon. Sila ay buhay at sandigan ng pag-unlad ng industriya ayon kay Karl Marx, ang manggagawa ang tunay na prodyuser ng bansa. Isa mahalagang salik ng produksiyon ay ang paggawa (*labor*). Nangangahulugan ito na kailangan ang manggagawa sa transpormasyon o pagbabagong anyo ng mga hilaw na materyales sa pagbuo ng tapos na produkto. Lubos na napakikinabangan ang ibang saik ng produksiyon sa tulong ng paggawa. Ito ang paggamit ng lakas, kakayahan at talino ng tao upang makatulong sa produksiyon. Naisasakatuparan ang mga gawaing pag-ekonomiya sapagkat sa lubos na paggamit ng mga manggagawa ng kanilang lakas at kakayahan upang makalihka ng mga produkto at serbisyo.

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Mga Uri ng Paggawa

May dalawang klasipikasyon ng manggagawa ito ay ang mga manggagawang pisikal at manggagawang mental. Ang manggagawang pisikal ay inuuri bilang *unskilled*, *semiskilled* at *skilled*. Sila ay nabibilang sa *blue-collar job*. Ang *blue collar job* ay tumutukoy sa gawain ng mga manggagawang mas higit na ginagamit kanilang lakas pisikal at enerhiya sa paglikha ng produkto at serbisyo. Ang gawain ng manggagawa na mas ginagamit ang mental na kapasidad at kaisipan ay nabibilang sa *white collar job*.

mga larawan ng iba't ibang klasipikasyon

Gawain sa Pagkakatuto Bilang 1:

Tukuyin kung anong klasipikasyon ng manggagawa ang mga sumusunod isulat kung ito ay manggagawang pisikal o manggagawang mental.

- | | |
|---------------------------|---------------------------------|
| _____ 1. konduktor ng bus | _____ 6. nagtitinda sa palengke |
| _____ 2. Punong guro | _____ 7. labandera |
| _____ 3. Karpintero | _____ 8. Teller sa banko |
| _____ 4. arkitekto | _____ 9. manager |
| _____ 5. elektrisyan | _____ 10. kusinero |

PESO Los Banos

Ang PESO o Public Employment Service Office ay isang multi-service facility na itinatag upang magbigay impormasyon sa trabaho at tulong sa mga kliyente ng Department of Labor and Employment (DOLE) at mga nasasakupan ng Local Government Unit (LGU).

Ang PESO Los Banos ay matatagpuan sa municipal building ng pamahalaan ng Los Banos. Sa panahon ng dating punong bayan ng Los Banos, na si Hon. Ceasar Perez nabuo ang tinawag na CAESAR - PESO, ito ay matatagpuan sa Gabaldon Building, dito hinuhubog ang mga manggagawa na nais magkaroon ng sertipiko upang magamit sa pagpasok ng trabaho. Ang mga training programs ng PCLBMSTC ay handog ng Sangguniang Bayan ng Los Baños, sa tulong ng Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA). Mayroong pitong kursong inilaan ang Public Employment Services Office (PESO) para sa mga mamamayan ng Los Baños: Shielded Metal Arc Welding, Electrical Maintenance, Basic Computer Literacy, Hilot Wellness and Massage Therapy, Dressmaking, Hairdressing at Bread and Pastry making

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Taong 2018, nagdaos ng pagtatapos ang mahigit 200 trainees sa kanilang pagsasanay. Layunin ng mga programang ito na mabigyan ng sapat na kaalaman at kasanayan sa iba'tibang uri ng trabaho ang mga trainees upang magkaroon sila ng hanapbuhay.

Natigil ang pagsasanay ng mga bagong trainees noong magpatupad ng ECQ dahil na

Ang mga trainees na maghihintay sa kanilang pagtatapos sa pamamagitan ng ilalim ng MECQ rin sa pandemyang COVID-19.

Taong 2021 nagplano ang pamahalaan ng PESO na naggasagawa ng on-line-job training, dahil sa ang pangangailangan ay face-to-face kahit nasa ilalim ng MECQ nagpatupad ng mga restriction sa pagsasanay. Naging matagumpay ang programa at nakapagbigayng maraming oportunidad para sa hanapbuhay.

Sa ngayon patuloy pa rin ang pagsasanay sa mga nais na magkaroon ng kaalaman sa larangan ng paggawa. Nagsasagawa ng mga anunsyo ang pamahalaan para sa mga nais lumahok sa programa ito ng pamahalaan ng Los Banos gamit ang iba't-ibang platform. Sa kanilang Facebook page matatagpuan ang mga programang inululunsad. Madalas ang kanilang Facebook page ay naglalaman ng mga impormasyon ng mga trabaho na kinakailangan sa iba't ibang industriya sa mga karating bayan at maging sa kamaynilaan. Nagsasagawa din sila ng tinatawag na Job Fair sa iba't ibang baranggay upang mas higit na mapalawig ang impormasyon para sa mga naghahanap ng trabaho. Maraming uri ng trabaho ang kanilang ina-anunsiyo para sa kwalipikasyon na babagay sa iyong talento, hilig at edukasyon.

Kahalagahan ng Paggawa nalilinig ang mga

- hilaw na materyales
- Napoproseso ang mga hilaw na materyales galing agrikultura nalilinig ang mga
- likas na yaman
- Napapaandar at nagagamit ang mga makinarya at teknolohiya nakalilikha ng mga
- produktong kailangan ng bansa.

Karaniwang sa Agrikultura ang naging hanap buhay ng mga mamamayan ng Los Banos. Pagsasaka o paghahalaman at pangingsida ang pangunahing pinagkukunan ng pang-araw araw na gastusin. Bago pa man dumating ang mga kastila sagana ang bayan sa mga likas na yaman. Isang dahilan nito ay ang bayan ay nasa paanan ng maalamat na bundok ng Maria Makiling kung kaya't sinasabi na binibiyayaan ang mga mamamayan ng masaganang bunga mula sa puno ng bundok ng Makiling.

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Talahanayan ng mga manggagawa mula sa Agrikultura

Table 95. Occupation Groups, Year 2018-2019

Occupation Groups	Location	Number		
		Male	Female	Total
1. Farmers				
a. Crop (Rice)	Bayog Maahas	23 26	3 10	26 36
b. Orchard	-	-	-	-
c. Livestock and dairy	All brgys	-	-	-
d. Poultry	All brgys	-	-	-
2. Ornamental & Other Plant Growers	Cutflower Bayog Maahas	71 8	26 7	97 15
	Tropical Growers Batong malake Timugan	68 22	22 29	90 51
3. Other Animal Producers	-	-	-	-
4. Aqua-Farm Cultivators	Coastal brgys	-	-	131
5. Other Farm Workers Not Elsewhere Classified	-	-	-	-
6. Fishermen	-	-	-	-
a. Inland Waters	Coastal brgys and Lalakay	-	-	693
b. Coastal Waters	Coastal brgys and Lalakay	-	-	-
c. Deep Sea	-	218	97	1139

Source: OMA Animal Population Survey 2018-2019

Sa Talahanayan na nasa itaas dito ipinakikita ang dami ng bilang ng mga manggagawa na nasa sektor ng Agrikultura,

Gawain sa Pagkakatuto Bilang 2

Sagutin ang mga katanungan

1. Anong mahalagang gampanin ng PESO Los Banos sa mamamayan nito?
2. Sa Paanong paraan nailalahad ng PESO ang pagtulong sa mga mamayan?
3. Anong Programa ang nagampanan ng dating punong bayan ng Los Banos, Hon. Caesar Perez para sa mga mamamayan ng Los Banos?
4. Sa inyong palagay kapakipakinabang ba ang PESO sa mga naninirahan sa isang banyan?
5. Paano nakatutulong ang ahensya ng PESO sa isang bayan?

Kahalagahan ng Agrikultura sa mga mangagawa

Ang Agrikultura ang naging sandigan ng hanapbuhay ng mamamayan ng Los Banos kahit noon pang panahon bago dumating ang kastila sa ating bansa. Sinsabi na sa Agrikultura unang nakilala ang bayan na ito. Taong 1909 isang Botanista ang nagtatag ng Unibesidad ng Pilipinas sangay sa Los Banos, Laguna. Hindi nakapagtataka kung bakit halos lahat ng manggagawa noon ay sa Agrikultura namumuhay, naging kultura na ang paghahalaman dahil na rin sa masaganang lupa. Kung kaya't iba't-ibang uri ng paghahalaman ang sumungaw sa bayan at naging pangunahing hanapbuhay ng marami rito.

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Kilala ang Barangay Bayog ng Los Baños, Laguna sa larangan ng aster farming. Simula pa noong 1970, marami na sa mga tagarito ang nabubuhay sa pag-aalaga ng bulaklak. napasa pasa na ng henerasyon ang pagtatanim ng aster. Ang samahan ng Bayog Flower Farmers Association ang nagbibigay ng kabuhayan ang marami sa mga taga Bayog.

Taniman ng Aster sa Brgy. Bayog.

Ang aster ay pinong-pinong mga bulaklak na para bang ubod-liit na mga daisies. Mula sa salitang Griyego ang "aster" na ang ibig sabihin sa Filipino ay "bituin." Tila nga naman libo-libong bituin ang mga aster na nakalatag sa mga pilapil ng Bayog. Dilaw ang gitna at kulay puti o lila ang mga talulot nito, pero mas pangkaraniwan ang kulay puti. Ang aster ay ginagamit na filler para sa mga flower arrangement gaya ng corsage at bouquet para sa kasal, sa dekorasyon sa grand opening ng mga establisimento o sa mga pagtatapos ng mga mag aral, pati na rin sa korona ng patay. Dahil sa tanyag at marami ang umaangkat sa halaman na ito dumami ang mga magtatanim at nagluluwas ng halamang Aster. Ang International Rice Research Institute (IRRI) o pandaigdigang Surian sa Pananaliksik ng Palay ang nag-ambag ng Green Revolution noong 1960 hanggang 1970 dahil sa paglikha nito ng mga uri ng bigas na may mataas ng ani na ginamit sa mga iba't ibang bansa sa Asya gaya ng Pilipinas at India. Ito ang institusyong nagbigay ng malaking bilang ng manggawa sa mamayan ng Los Banos, Masasabing na ang iba't-ibang uri ng mga manggagawa ay empleyado sa institusyong ito. Maging ang mga banyaga na dito nakabase para sa pananaliksik ay kabilang na manggagawa. Malaki ang naging ambag ng institusyong ito sa paglilingkod na siya nagbibigay ng kasiglahan sa sektor ng paglilingkod sa bayan ng Los Banos. Ang iba't-ibang departamento ng IRRI ay may iba't-ibang manggagawa na siyang lilinang at magpoproseso ng iba't-ibang produkto at serbisyo, kaya't marami ang nabibigyan ng trabaho.

Mga Bumubuo sa Sektor ng Paglilingkod

Ang sektor na ito ay tumutukoy sa sektor na nagbibigay ng serbisyo sa transportasyon, komunikasyon, media, pangangalakal, pananalapi, serbisyo mula sa pamahalaan, at turismo, ito ang sektor na umaalalay sa buong yugto ng produksiyon, distribusyon, kalakalan, at pagkonsumo ng mga produkto sa loob o labas ng bansa. Kabilang sa sektor ng paglilingkod ang subsektor ng mga sumusunod:

- pananalapi insurance
- komersiyo real estate
- kalakalang pakyawan
- kalakalang pagtitingi
- transportasyon
- Kasama sa pag unlad ng bayan ng Los Banos ang pagkakaroon ng maraming industriya na nangangailangan ng paglilingkod ng manggawa, dahil dito malaking oportunidad sa mga mamamayan ang sila ay magkaroon ng hanapbuhay. Ngunit kabila ng lahat may mga manggagawa pa rin ang nagtungo sa ibang bansa upang doon ay magtrabaho kapalit ng magandang buhay na maibibigay nila sa kanilang pamilya.

Talahanayan ng mga manggagawa mula sa ibang bansa na naninirahan sa Los Banos

II. Number of overseas Filipino workers (OFWs)

Table 65. Number of Overseas Filipino Workers (OFWs) by Barangay Year 2017

Barangay	Total Population	Resident population	Overseas Filipino Workers (OFWs)	Non-working individuals
1. Anos	5442	5172	131	139
2. Bagong Silang	593	579	7	7
3. Bambang	6161	5778	189	194
4. Batong Malake	8125	7922	97	106
5. Baybayin	1509	1448	30	31
6. Bayog	10183	9644	260	279
7. Lalakay	4028	3853	85	90
8. Masahas	8404	7998	197	209
9. Malinta	6240	5986	120	134
10. Mayondon	13264	12627	309	328
11. San Antonio	10245	9958	199	148
12. Tadlac	3336	3186	73	77
13. Timugan	5000	4742	125	155
14. Tuntungin-Putho	8137	7705	209	223

Source: CBMS 2017

Gawain sa Pagkakatuto Bilang 3: Ibigay ang tamang sagot ng mga sumusunod na katanungan

- _____ 1. Isang institusyon na pinag aaralan ang iba't ibang uri ng kanin na nagkakaloob ng maraming manggagawa.
- _____ 2. Taon kung kailan natatag ang Unibersidad ng Pilipinas.
- _____ 3. Uri ng halaman na siyang pinagkukunan ng trabaho sa barangay Bayog.
- _____ 4. Katangian ng bulaklak na matatagpuan sa barangay Bayog.
- _____ 5. Rebolusyon inambag ng pamunuan ng IRRI noong panahon ni Marcos.
- _____ 6. Barangay sa bayan ng Los Banos na may pinakamaraming manggagawa sa labas ng ating bansa.

Gawain sa Pagkakatuto Bilang 3: Ibigay ang tamang sagot ng mga sumusunod na katanungan

- _____1. Isang institusyon na pinag aaralan ang iba't ibang uri ng kanin na nagkakaloob ng maraming manggagawa.
- _____2. Taon kung kailan natatag ang Unibersidad ng Pilipinas.
- _____3. Uri ng halaman na siyang pinagkukunan ng trabaho sa barangay Bayog.
- _____4. Katangian ng bulalalak na matatagpuan sa barangay Bayog.
- _____5. Rebolusyon inambag ng pamunuan ng IRRI noong panahon ni Marcos.
- _____6. Barangay sa bayan ng Los Banos na may pinakamaraming manggagawa sa labas ng ating bansa.
- _____7. Ang malawakang sakit ang nagpatigil sa pagsasanay sa Los Banos ng mga tao nais magkaroon ng kasanayan sa larangan ng pagtatrabaho.
- _____8. Isang programa ng dating Mayor Perez.
- _____9. Salitang pinangalingan ng Aster
- _____10. Dalawang uri ng manggagawa?

Gawain sa Pagka

katuto Bilang 4: Bigyan ng sariling paliwanag ang mensahe ng nasa larawan. Iisulat ang inyong sagot sa inyong kwaderno.

Gawain sa Pagkakatuto Bilang 5: Kompletuhin ang graph sa ibaba. Tukuyin ang mahalagang papel na ginagampanan ng pamahalaan sa mga manggagawa upang makabuo ng konklusyon.

KALAKALAN AT TURISMO SA BAYAN LOS BAN LOS

Week 6-7

Mga Layunin:

Sa araling ito, inaasahang ...

- matataya ang kalakaran sa kalakaran sa loob at labas ng bayan ng los banos
- masusuri ang ugnayan ng mga karatig at malayong lugar pati na rin ang panlabas ng bansa sa kalakaran.
- mapahahalagahan ang mga natatanging turismo ng bayan ng Los Banos
- makatutulong sa pagpapakilala sa turismo sa pamamagitan ng pakikipag ugnayan sa ibang

Mahalagang Terminolohiya

- kalakaran
- turismo
- panlabas na sektor

Pagpapahalaga:

- paggalang sa kultura
- pagtanaw sa nakaraan

Isang hamon sa Lokal na pamahalaan ang mapaunlad ang kalakaran at turismo ng isang bayan. Isa sa pinaguukulan ng pamahalaan ay ang pakikipagkalakaran sa mga bayan, probinsya at rehiyon, maging sa ibang bansa ang pakikipag ugnayan sa mga organisadong pangkat na may kinalaman sa ekonomiya. Ang kalakaran ay pagpapalitan ng mga produkto at serbisyo ng dalawang panig. Tinatawag na kalakalang panloob kapag ito ay nagaganap lamang sa loob ng bansa, kalakalang panlabas kapag ang kalakaran ay nagaganap sa pagitang ng 2 bansa.

source: Facebook LB page

Gawain sa Pagkakatuto Bilang 1

Sagutan ang mga katanungan at isulat ang sagot sa sagutang papel

1. Ano ang nais ipaabot na mensahe ng punong bayan ng Los Banos?
2. Paano mapapaunlad ang kalakaran ng pamahalaan sa Los Banos? Ayon sa anunsiyo
3. Ano ang kinalaman ng mahalagang magagampanan ng imprastruktura sa kalakaran sa bayan ng Los Banos?

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Kalakalan sa bayan ng Los Banos

Ang kalakalan pang bayan ay lumawig sa tulong ng estasyon ng tren na binuksan noong Agosto 15, 1910 at ito ay matatagpuan sa Barangay ng Bambang. Tinaguriang daang bakal ng tren na siyang nagluluwas ng kalakal gulay ang naging pangunahing produkto na siyang dinadala sa ibang bayan at probinsya. Naging matagumpay ang kalakalan dahil na rin naragdagan ng iba't ibang produkto ang inululuwas na galing sa bayan ng Los Banos. Ang Aster at mga kakanin na yari ng mga negosyante ay naging bahagi rin ng kalakalan. Hindi lang Tren ang naging transportasyon para sa kalakal pati ang bus ay naging bahagi

rin ng kalakalan patungong Manila. Source: Lumang Estasyon sa Bambang Los Banos

Masigla ang kalakalan kahit mahirap ang transportasyon ngunit marami pa rin mga produkto ang nakararating sa bayan ng Los Banos at nailuluwas. Ginamit din sa kalakalan ang Bus patungong Manila. Sa palengke kung saan doon makikita ang mga produkto at sentro ng kalakalan.

Ang mga halamang Orchid na noon ay pinamamahalaan ng isang organisasyon na siyang nagpaunlad ng kalakalan noon sa halaman. Ang organisasyon ay binuuo ng

Source: wlkmap. Lumang bus na transportasyon paatungo

Manila mga asawa ng dating propesor sa UPCA

Rattan Furniture Bussiness

Ayon sa ulat ng Times opisyal na publikasyon ng bayan ng Los Banos taong 1999 ng magsimula ang negosyo ng Rattan ng punong tagapamahala ng Remd Davies Enterprises na naka base sa Pampangga at may tindahan din dito sa bayan na ito, ito ay. Inululuwas nila ang mga muwebles na yari sa rattan. Dinadala nila ito sa mga opisya at mga residente na nagnanais na magkaroon ng ganitong uri ng furniture.

Panghimagas na pasalubong

Tinagurian ang Los Baños bilang "home of the famous buko pie." Ang buko pie ay isang tradisyonal na panghimagas na gawa sa laman ng niyog at madalas ay ibinibenta nang mainit-init pa ng mga naglalako. Maraming sikat na pangalan ang nagkukompetensya sa pagbebenta ng buko pie tulad ng Lety's, Colette's at The Original Buko Pie Bakeshop.

Ang baranggay ng Anos ay naging sentro ng kalakalan ng mga pagkain na ipinasasalubong gng mga dumarayo o dumadaan sa bayan ng Los

Banos . Ang recipe ng buko pie ng Orient ay binuo noong 1965 ng kapatid ng may-ari na si Soledad Pahud, si Nanette Risano. Si Ms. Risano ay nageksperimento sa maraming iba't ibang uri ng pie noong siya ay nag-aaral kung paano magluto.

sprace: WSJ.com

Ngunit ang kanyang buko pie ay naging isang hit, na humantong sa kanya upang ilunsad ang unang specialty buko pie shop sa Pilipinas. Hanggang sa marami pang negosyante ang nagluto na rin ng buko pie, kaya't iba't ibang pangalan ang nagsimula ng kanilang negosyo.

Noong 1965	Kalakalan	Bambang	Tren	Rattan
Agosto 15, 1910	Orchid	Daang Bakal	Bus	Los Banos

Gawain sa Pagkatuto Bilang 2: Isulat ang tamang sagot sa inyong sagutang papel. Piliin ang sagot sa loob ng kahon.

1. Ito ay pagpapalitan ng mga produkto at serbisyo ng dalawang panig
2. Ito ang unang naging kasangkapan sa pagluluwas ng kalakal
3. Ito ang tawag sa dinaraan ng Tren.
4. Taon ng binuo ang recipe ng buko pie.
5. Halaman na naging sentro ng kalakalan sa na pinamumunuan ng mga dating asawa ng propesor ng UPLB.
6. Isang barangay sa Los Banos kung saan naroroon ang estasyon ng Tren.
7. Petsa ng pagkakatag ng estasyon ng Tren sa Los Banos
8. Ito ang sinasakyan ng mga kalakal patungong Maynila.
9. Tahanan ng Most Famoust Buko Pie.
10. Yari ang mga mwebles na inululuwas sa ibang bayan at probinsiya.

Gawain sa Pagkatuto Bilang 3: Ibigay ang inyong opinyon tungkol sa usaping
 “Kalakalan tanda ng tagumpay ng bayan o sanhi ng kakulangan ng
 produkto sa bayan “

Ang iba't-ibang *Tourist Spot* ng Los Baños

Dahil na rin sa mala alamat na kasaysayan at makasaysayan ang bayan, naging sentro rin ng turismo itong bayan. Maraming magagandang lugar ang nakahimlay na siyang pinapasayalan ng mga lokal nating kababayan maging mga dayuhan sa ating bansa ay napapa-ibig rin puntahan.

Ang Bundok Makiling, o Bundok Maquiling, ay isang natutulog na bulkan na matatagpuan sa hangganan ng lalawigan ng Laguna at Batangas sa isla ng Luzon, Pilipinas. Ang bundok ay tumataas sa isang elevation na 1,090 m above mean sea level at ito ang pinakamataas na katangian ng Laguna Volcanic Field. Ang bulkan ay walang naitalang makasaysayang pagsabog ngunit ang bulkan ay nakikita pa rin sa pamamagitan ng geothermal features tulad ng mud spring at hot spring.

ng Makiling Botanic Gardens ay matatagpuan sa Los Baños, Laguna, Pilipinas. Ito ay sumasakop sa 300 ektarya at bahagi ng Mount Makiling Forest Reserve. Itinatag noong 1965, ito ay isang pasilidad ng pananaliksik at edukasyon ng Unibersidad ng Pilipinas Los Baños (UPLB). Layunin ng mga hardin na pangalagaan at

Source Reywolsen Fortes

ipakita ang iba't ibang uri ng halaman.

Mayroon silang mga orchid, ferns, palms, bamboos, at endemic na halaman. May mga may temang hardin tulad ng Orchidarium at Medicinal Plants Garden. Ang mga hardin ay tahimik at maganda, perpekto para sa mga mahilig sa kalikasan. Nagbibigay sila ng magandang karanasan para sa mga bisita. Ang mga hardin ay well-maintained at nag-aalok ng mapayapang kapaligiran. Madaling mapupuntahan ang mga hardin at nagbibigay ng nakakarelaks na bakasyon. Ang mga hardin ay isang buhay na museo ng mga halaman. Nagbibigay sila ng pagkakataon na pahalagahan ang kagandahan ng kalikasan. Ang mga hardin ay isang santuwaryo ng mga halaman at hayop. Nag-aambag sila sa pag-iingat ng pagkakaiba-iba ng halaman. Ang mga ito ay patunay ng kahalagahan ng pangangalaga sa kapaligiran. Mainam rin ito sa mga mag-aaral na nagsasaliksik tungkol sa mga iba't-ibang uri ng halaman.

Yamashita Shrine - Noong Oktubre 29, 1945, si YAMASHITA ay kinasuhan bilang isang war criminal ng isang military tribunal sa Maynila. Hinatulan si Yamashita ng bitay sa kasong pag masaker sa mga Pilipino at Amerikano sa Los Banos Laguna. Si Toyuki Yamashita at ang mga kasamang niya sundalong hapon ay ang namuno sa pagpatay. Binitay siya sa Economic Garden sa Los Banos. Pinapasyalan ng mga kababayan nivang hapones ang shrine na ito bilang pagbibigay pugay kay General Yamashita.

Dampalit Falls-
kumukuha ng atraksyon

ang Falls na ito sa mga turista lokal man o internasyonal, dahil na rin sa ganda ng kapaligiran at malamig na tubig. Ito ay ay isang maliit na kilalang talon na matatagpuan sa Mt. Makiling Nature Reserve sa Los Banos, Laguna. Kapag ang tubig ay malakas na bumabagsak sa catch basin nakalilikha ng isang swimming hole.

Gawain sa Pagkatuto Bilang 4: Punan ng tamang sagot ang mga patlang

1. Ang _____ ay isang natutulog na bulkan na makikita sa bayan ng Los Banos.
2. Sa _____ naganap ang pag massacre ng mga hapon sa mga sibilyangFilipino at Amerikano.
3. Ang _____ ay matatagpuan ang maraming hardin.
4. _____ aay isang maliit na Talon na matatagpuan sa Lalakaya Los Banos Laguna.
5. _____ Ang Heneral na binitay dahil sa pagpatay ng maraming sibilyan na hinostage sa Baker Hall ng Unibersidad.

Tiyakin:

Sagutin ang tanong sa harap ng klase.

Bakit kailangang makipagkalakalan ang isang bayan?

Talasanggunian

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ECOLOGICAL PROFILE (2021) MGLB-OMA Agriculture Profile 2021 , MCME Files 2015-2020 & MGLB-OMA Agriculture Profile 2017 & 2021

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Ethical considerations were meticulously integrated into every facet of the research process in the development and validation of localized supplementary instructional materials for Araling Panlipunan 9 at Los Baños National High School-Poblacion. The study adhered to the ethical guidelines outlined in the Laguna College of Business and Arts research manual and was subjected to scrutiny by the LCBA Ethics and Integrity Board.

To establish a foundation of ethical conduct, appropriate letters of consent were provided to Los Baños National High School-Poblacion and the participating Grade 9

learners. These letters elucidated the study's objectives, emphasized the voluntary nature of participation, and assured the confidentiality of the participants' information.

In alignment with the Data Privacy Act of 2012, stringent measures were implemented to safeguard the personal data of the respondents. No personal information obtained from the participants was disclosed or shared with any third party during the research process. Maintaining confidentiality and data security was paramount to ensure the privacy and anonymity of the respondents.

Furthermore, the researcher upheld academic integrity by diligently citing all sources and references used in the study. Proper citation of ideas, hypotheses, and expressions attributed them to their original sources, preserving scholarly integrity and mitigating the risk of plagiarism.

By prioritizing ethical principles, the researcher ensured the rights, privacy, and well-being of the participants were safeguarded throughout the study. The research was conducted with the utmost respect for ethical standards, thereby ensuring the responsible and ethical conduct of the research process.

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